

TRANSCEND

Transdisciplinary methods for societal impact assessment and impact creation for security research technologies

D3.2 – Pilots: Final Report

WP3 – Implementing Responsible Research and Innovation in Security Research; Insights from four Test Cases.

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Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the results of the TRANSCEND pilot activities aimed at testing and validating strategies to enhance citizen participation in security research, based on Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) principles.

Chapter 2 outlines the TRANSCEND methodology for the planning and implementation of citizen engagement activities in technology development using the Participatory Impact Pathways Analysis (PIPA) approach.

Chapter 3 deals with the Cybersecurity Pilot, focusing on measures to protect computer networks and data from unauthorized access, thereby safeguarding organisations and citizens. Despite the technical complexity and transparency issues, citizen involvement can enhance cyber awareness, resilience, trust, and innovation, especially in areas impacting daily life. Collaborating with three research projects, the pilot activities explored ways to make cybersecurity applications more citizen-centric, addressing challenges like recruitment difficulties and contextual adaptation.

Chapter 4 presents the Disaster Resilient Societies pilot aimed at improving the Team Österreich app—a digital platform for disaster preparedness and response developed by the Austrian Red Cross. Workshops focused on adapting the app to better meet the needs of volunteers and professionals in crisis situations. Participants evaluated the app's functionality and provided suggestions for improvement, such as enhanced zoom features and downloadable checklists, with positive feedback on the usefulness of the TRANSCEND guidelines for successful engagement.

Chapter 5 presents the Fighting Crime and Terrorism pilot, conducted in partnership with the City of Mechelen (Belgium), focusing on urban security. The pilot explored ways to encourage citizens, especially young people, to participate in discussions about urban safety and preventing radicalisation. Through co-creation workshops, participants collaborated on strategies to enhance security and mitigate radicalization risks, fostering trust and innovation, with feedback emphasizing successful engagement and valuable insights for improving urban security policies.

Chapter 6 presents the results of the Border Management pilot, aimed at promoting citizen involvement in the use of technological systems at borders. It addresses especially the challenge of engaging civil society organisations (CSOs) to improve transparency and effectiveness in border management practices. Workshops gathered different stakeholders and put CSOs perspectives at the centre, focusing on innovations that better serve public needs while ensuring security. Feedback highlighted the importance and difficulty of CSO involvement in refining technologies and promoting inclusive practices.

Chapter 7 summarises common issues of the pilots at a high level and provides recommendations for the successful practical implementation of citizen engagement in safety and security research and innovation (R&I) activities using the TRANSCEND guidelines.

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List of acronyms/abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ALIGNER	Artificial Intelligence Roadmap for Policing and Law Enforcement (Project)
APET	African Union Panel on Emerging Technologies
AutRC/ARC	<i>Österreichisches Rotes Kreuz</i> (Austrian Red Cross)
BM	Border management
CIP	Critical Infrastructure Provider
CS	Cybersecurity
CSO	Civil Society Organisation
CYLENCE	Detection of Cyber Bullying and Hate Speech (Project)
DISSS	Dutch Institute for Safe and Secure Spaces
DRR	Disaster Risk Reduction
DRS	Disaster Resilient Societies
ECRIS-TCN	European Criminal Records Information System–Third Country Nationals
Efus	<i>Le Forum Européen pour la Sécurité Urbaine</i> (European Forum for Urban Security)
EPLO	European Public Law Organization
ETIAS	European Travel Information and Authorisation System
EU	European Union
FCT	Fight against Crime and Terrorism

Abbreviation	Explanation
Fraunhofer	Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft zur Förderung der angewandten Forschung e.V.
FRT	Facial Recognition Technology
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
MoI	Memorandum of Understanding
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
ORF	<i>Österreichischer Rundfunk</i> (Austrian Broadcasting)
PAROMA-MED	Privacy Aware and Privacy Preserving Distributed and Robust Machine Learning for Medical Applications (Project)
R&D	Research and Development
R&I	Research and Innovation
ROJM	<i>Regionaal Open Jeugdcentrum Mechelen</i> (Regional Open Youth Centre Mechelen)
RRI	Responsible research and innovation
RTD	Research, Technology and Development
SIS	Schengen Information System
WP	Work Package
PIPA	Participatory Impact Pathways Analysis

Table 1-1: List of acronyms/abbreviations

Glossary of terms

Term	Explanation
Border Management	A thematic term used in European security research programming, border management focuses on external EU borders, and it covers a wide array of measures dealing with border crossings. In the security domain, it refers to border control practices to identify and manage security risks and protect fundamental rights. Border management is one of the pilot domains.
Citizen	The main stakeholders in TRANSCEND are grouped according to the different contexts - political, scientific, societal - and can therefore also be a guide for the selection of stakeholders in the pilot processes for the TRANSCEND project. Citizen, where used, is to be understood loosely to mean members of the public, as distinguished from persons working in an official capacity and not through their legal rights to citizenship. The project does include non-citizens in the legal understanding of the term.
Citizen involvement	Refers to involvement further than Civil Society Organisations towards civil society in the broad sense or as understood through the concept of citizen science.
Cybersecurity	A thematic term used in European security research programming. It refers to the practice of securing electronic data and systems against attack. It is one of the pilot domains.

<p>Disaster Resilient Societies</p>	<p>A thematic term used in European security research programming. It refers to disaster risk management and governance through improved capacities for first responders and societal resilience. It is one of the pilot domains.</p>
<p>Fighting Crime and Terrorism</p>	<p>A thematic term used in European security research programming. It refers to efforts towards the prevention of crime and terrorism and the detection and mitigation of their potential consequences. It is one of the pilot domains.</p>
<p>Safety</p>	<p>When someone or something is protected from harm, especially from unintentional harms, like natural disasters or technical malfunction.</p>
<p>Security</p>	<p>The act of protecting people, organisations or objects from harms, including intentional threats and dangers, like cybercrimes.</p>
<p>Stakeholder</p>	<p>Interested and affected persons and groups. Understood as representative of two directions: how the project affects them; and how we intend to enable them to affect the project.</p>

Table 1-2: Glossary of terms

1 Introduction

1.1 Background

In the EU, particularly in the context of policies that promote R&I in the Union, security research “targets technology areas that correspond as closely as possible to the security needs of the Union”, i.e., those with the highest threat and/or capability development needs (European Commission, 2004, p. 16; Friedewald *et al.*, 2023). These priority areas comprise five problem-oriented thematic areas, which are referred to as “objectives”: (1) Fighting Crime and Terrorism (FCT), (2) Border Management (BM), (3) Resilient Infrastructures, (4) Cybersecurity (CS), (5) Disaster-Resilient Societies (DRS). Each of these objectives includes several sub-themes, e.g., the FCT objective includes sub-themes such as technologies to support law enforcement agencies (information analysis, forensics, enhanced intelligence to detect and deter organised crime, etc.), approaches to prevent, detect, and deter urgent forms of crime such as cybercrime and terrorism, radicalisation, and domestic or sexual violence.¹ As security is considered a vital techno-social issue of our times, all stakeholders and affected parties have an important part to play to ensure that solutions work while protecting our rights. Strategies and institutions have been built to protect and defend assets crucial to the state, economy, and society against potential threats. However, the various actors involved and affected might have different interests, (technical) capabilities, and power to enforce them.

The involvement of those who are ultimately affected by a technology or technology-enabled social practice has long been considered a blind spot. This includes those most affected as well as the general public or at least civil society organisations (CSOs) that act as representatives and advocates of their interests. TRANSCEND's pilot activities aim to contribute to addressing the underrepresentation of affected persons, the public, and, in particular, civil society organisations in security research. This is done by addressing structural and methodological challenges and by developing, testing, and evaluating suitable procedures.

In this report, we present the procedures of planning and implementation of these pilots based on the principles of Responsible Research and Innovation.² In addition to the planning steps, we also include the learnings from pilots, with sections presenting the assessment results from all the pilots and a section reporting the methodological findings on the further development of the TRANSCEND Toolbox “Unlocking Voices: Practical Methods to Engage Citizens in Safety and Security Innovation” (see Steen, Afghani and Garstka, 2025).

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/wp-call/2023-2024/wp-6-civil-security-for-society_horizon-2023-2024_en.pdf

² https://commission.europa.eu/research-and-innovation_en

1.2 Objectives

Operational planning for the case studies encompassed defining the specific issues addressed, choosing the involved actors, and establishing a detailed framework for content, activities, processes, and timelines (Friedewald *et al.*, 2023). To maximise the transfer of knowledge and experience to subsequent pilots, these studies were conducted sequentially rather than concurrently. Local partners, typically CSOs, carried out fieldwork, actively involving community actors. Special attention was given to ensuring a diverse sampling of citizens, including marginalised and vulnerable groups, while striving for gender equality. The concrete design of the four pilots was tailored to reflect their unique characteristics, employing effective formats and techniques developed in WP1 (Garstka *et al.*, 2023; Afghani *et al.*, 2024). Overall, the implementation of the pilots aims to use proven and easy-to-use formats and techniques to promote and strengthen social participation and engagement and thus achieve a positive social impact.

1.3 Structure of the report

This deliverable begins with a chapter explaining the approach to the TRANSCEND pilots, describing the methodological approach that was used to conduct the pilot activities.

The next four chapters cover, for each of the application areas, the organisation of the activities, the choice of methodology, the implementation and results of the workshop, the lessons learned, as well as a summary and outlook. They are arranged as follows:

- Pilot #1: Cybersecurity (CS)
- Pilot #2: Disaster-Resilient Societies (DRS)
- Pilot #3: Fighting Crime and Terrorism (FCT)
- Pilot #4: Border Management (BM)

Following the description of the individual pilot activities, a cross-sectional overview of the pilot activities follows. This section compares the pilots in terms of four fundamental principles and provides detailed recommendations on how to successfully organise citizen participation in security research.

1.4 Relationship to other TRANSCEND deliverables

Del. #	Deliverable description	Status	Relationship with D3.2
1.1	State of the art in methods for citizen and societal engagement	submitted	This deliverable informed WP3 about available methods of citizen participation.
1.2	State of the art in ethical, human rights and societal impact assessment	accepted	This deliverable informed WP3 about available schemes for assessing impacts.
1.3	TRANSCEND Toolbox v1	accepted	This deliverable—based on the work in D1.1 and D1.2 is providing the initial Toolbox that was used in the first pilot activities (DRS, FCT).
1.4	TRANSCEND Toolbox v2	submitted	This deliverable is an extended version of D1.3 and was used for the DRS, FCT and CS pilot activities
1.5	TRANSCEND Toolbox v3	submitted	This deliverable is an extended and improved version of D1.3 and D1.4 and was used for the FCT, CS and BM pilot activities
1.6	TRANSCEND Toolbox v4	submitted	This deliverable is the final version of the Toolbox.
2.1	Landscape of security research CSO: Mapping, Strategies and Best Practices for Citizen and Societal Engagement	accepted	This deliverable provided the basis for the planning of the pilots in WP3 for the selection of CSOs representing specific citizen interests.
3.1	Pilot strategy	accepted	This deliverable outlined the concept for planning and implementing the pilot activities that are documented in this report.

2 Approach for the pilot activities

To support the integration of citizen and societal engagement into the pilot activities, the “Participatory Impact Pathways Analysis” or PIPA methodology was used. This approach ensured that the evaluation of engagement efforts was embedded from the outset of the pilots, allowing for ongoing reflection, learning, and adaptation. In this way, the methodological foundations have been directly applied in practice, guiding both the planning and evaluation phases of the pilot activities.

PIPA is a practical approach for planning, monitoring, and evaluating transdisciplinary projects (cf. Van Drooge and Spaapen, 2022). It brings together a range of stakeholders — from project team members to targeted participants — to co-create a roadmap towards achieving the project’s intended impact. By facilitating inclusive discussions, PIPA enhances understanding of how stakeholder engagement contributes to project success.

PIPA helps project teams articulate their “impact pathways” (theories of action), develop logic models, and use these models to guide planning and evaluation (Alvarez *et al.*, 2010). This makes it especially valuable for complex fields like security research, whether in cybersecurity, border control, the fight against crime and terrorism, or disaster management, where success depends not just on technological solutions but also on effective stakeholder collaboration. Policymakers, law enforcement, local communities, and international actors all play critical roles. PIPA provides a structured way to map these relationships, clarify roles, and strengthen engagement strategies.

Importantly, PIPA is not a rigid template. It is designed to be tailored to the specific needs and context of each project (Douthwaite *et al.*, 2011–2014). We selected PIPA for TRANSCEND because it offers a flexible, user-friendly method that produces tangible outputs while accommodating diverse stakeholder perspectives (STEPS Centre, 2022). Its adaptability makes it well-suited for the distinct needs of each TRANSCEND pilot.

PIPA guided the design and structure of our engagement Toolbox (cf. Steen, Afghani and Garstka, 2025, chapter 3). We primarily drew on the STEPS Centre’s PIPA methodology guide, adapting its key steps to align with TRANSCEND’s goals and pilot contexts. The adapted methodology follows four main phases.

TRANSCEND Approach for the pilot activities

Figure 2-1: TRANSCEND Approach for Pilot Activities

1. Start with a clear purpose and objectives

The first step was to establish a clear, shared understanding of each pilot's purpose and expected outcomes. To support this, the Toolbox "Unlocking Voices. Practical methods to engage citizens in safety and security innovation" (Steen, Afghani and Garstka, 2025) provides key discussion prompts and tools, such as the Stakeholder Engagement Questionnaire (Appendix A), Problem Tree Analysis Template (Appendix B), and Outcomes Logic Model (Appendix C). These resources helped teams collaboratively define the scope and direction of their pilot.

We used the following aspects to help pilot teams assess and document this step:

- *Clarity of the pilot's purpose:* Is the problem being addressed clearly defined, including relevant challenges and opportunities within the security field?
- *Shared understanding of objectives:* Have the goals been jointly discussed and agreed upon by all team members?
- *Formulation of key questions:* Are the main questions the pilot seeks to explore identified and understood?
- *Partner identification:* Have relevant stakeholders or partners for the pilot been identified?

2. Collaborate with relevant stakeholders

The next step focused on involving relevant stakeholders and aligning their contributions with the project's objectives. This involved clarifying each stakeholder's role and defining the areas of collaboration.

The following aspects guided this step:

- *Stakeholder mapping and analysis:* Have the relevant stakeholders been identified and their interests, roles, and influence assessed?

- *Alignment of stakeholder goals:* Have the goals and priorities of different partners been discussed and documented?
- *Topic selection for engagement:* Are the engagement topics aligned with the identified goals and interests of stakeholders?

3. Plan and execute interactions and meetings

Once the pilot's purpose was clearly defined and stakeholders were on board, the next step was to plan and implement engagement activities. Pilot teams were encouraged to select appropriate methods, prepare the event environment, and ensure inclusive participation.

The following aspects supported planning and implementation:

- *Justification for engagement method:* Is there a clear rationale for selecting a particular method, and how well does it suit the pilot's context?
- *Participant recruitment strategy:* What approach was used to recruit participants, and what were the outcomes? (see Steen, Afghani and Garstka, 2025, p. 19)
- *Event logistics and accessibility:* Were the venue and event environment adequately prepared, and were any special needs or considerations addressed to ensure meaningful participation?

4. Implement, evaluate, and document

TRANSCEND adopted an iterative, hands-on evaluation approach that supports continuous learning and adaptation. This phase included:

- *Regular reflexive sessions:* Weekly exchanges among TRANSCEND partners served as a space to jointly reflect on progress, challenges, and impact.
- *Documentation and knowledge sharing:* Partners were encouraged to log interactions, collect impact stories, and share learnings throughout the pilot. These insights have been consolidated in this deliverable.
- *Generating recommendations:* Evaluation outcomes informed guidance on effective stakeholder engagement in security research, covering communication strategies, engagement approaches, and capacity building.

Key aspects for this phase included:

- *Reflections on method selection:* What worked well? What challenges arose?
- *Feedback on the Toolbox:* What elements were most useful, and what could be improved?
- *Pilot workshop results:* What citizen needs and concerns were identified?

- *Lessons learned:* What insights emerged about citizens' requirements and the effectiveness of the methods used?

It should be noted that, for practical reasons, the PIPA approach described above could not be fully implemented in all thematic pilots, particularly in the earliest activities carried out. The requirements of the first two steps had already been defined as part of the 'Pilot Strategy' and were therefore explicitly considered by all four pilots. In step 3, there was considerable variation due to the wide range of topics, the formats chosen and the actors involved, particularly regarding participant recruitment and event logistics: For example, the pilot on Disaster resilient societies was largely implemented within the organisational context of the Austrian Red Cross. This meant that certain parameters had already been determined in advance. There were also variations in the implementation of the aspects identified as important for step 4, mainly for practical and pragmatic reasons. For example, it was not possible to reflect on whether citizen participation had led to actual improvements in safety technology or its use. This was because, within the framework of the pilot activities, interventions could only be carried out on a selective basis and not over the entire innovation cycle. Feedback from the citizens involved was also not always easy to obtain systematically, as the response rate to the feedback forms distributed was generally low.

Nevertheless, an attempt was made to carry out as comprehensive an assessment as possible, although some information is not documented in writing, for example because it was agreed with participants not to produce detailed written documentation. In such cases, our assessment is based on verbal reports from the project partners involved about the experience they have gained.

3 Pilot on Cybersecurity (CS)

3.1 Organisation of the pilot activities

The term cybersecurity covers all measures to protect computer networks, systems, and the data stored on them from unauthorised access or attacks by malicious actors. This also includes securing communications and transactions via computer networks as well as protection against crimes such as cyberbullying, misinformation, and cybercrime. Occasionally, defence measures against attacks in the context of a cyber war are also included under the term cybersecurity. Cybersecurity measures aim to prevent unlawful disclosure, theft or damage to hardware, software or data. They operate at different levels, such as the individual, organisational or national level. Cybersecurity is particularly important for government authorities, critical infrastructure such as the power grid, ports, and airports, as well as commercial companies (see also Steen, Afghani and Garstka, 2025, p. 49) Overall, it can be stated that the field of application contains aspects that make it difficult for citizens to easily engage:

- **Technical complexity:** The terminology and technical functionality are often complex and difficult to understand, making it difficult for non-experts to engage in a discussion about possible technology impacts.
- **Lack of transparency:** Many cybersecurity activities are in the hands of powerful state or industry actors who often do not communicate transparently about their actions and procedures or even keep details secret from the public.
- **Rapid change:** Technology is evolving rapidly, making it difficult for citizens to keep up and understand evolving security threats and countermeasures.
- **Trust issues:** Due to privacy concerns and cybercrime incidents, many people have a low level of trust in digital technologies and worry about security vulnerabilities.

These few aspects already make clear how complex and difficult to access the field of cybersecurity is. During the planning activities for the pilot, it became clear that this also applies to the researchers, including the TRANSCEND team. However, there are also many opportunities to approach cybersecurity research issues from the citizen's perspective. The following aspects show that collaborative research with citizens can help to reduce conceptual or technical complexity. In this way, they can contribute to making cybersecurity applications more citizen-centric.

- **Awareness:** Engaging citizens raises awareness of cybersecurity risks and practices, which can contribute to a safer online environment.
- **Reality-based and diverse perspectives:** Citizens bring valuable insights and experiences from their everyday lives that can help make security solutions practical and user-friendly.

- Strengthening resilience: By promoting skills and knowledge about technical solutions, citizens can better respond to cyber threats and protect themselves, increasing the overall resilience of society.
- Promoting trust: Transparent research and public involvement can increase trust in technologies and institutions, which is crucial for the acceptance of cybersecurity measures.
- Innovative solutions: Citizen participation can lead to creative and innovative approaches that may not be considered in “purely professional” research.
- Ethical and social aspects: Involving citizens helps to address ethical and social issues in cybersecurity research and ensure that measures meet the needs and values of society.

The following section explains how the above-mentioned application-specific aspects were incorporated into the planning of the pilots. Although the project proposal and our “Pilot strategy” (Friedewald *et al.*, 2023) set out several ideas on how to identify and motivate candidates for collaboration, it was not possible to define a pilot in a way that would have worked effectively for all involved parties—at least not under the framework conditions of a research project such as TRANSCEND.

The idea of realising the pilot activities with institutions with which the task leader had cooperated in other EU Framework projects could not be implemented, nor could the concept of cooperation with a network of cities—enabled by TRANSCEND partner EFUS (Friedewald *et al.*, 2025, section 4.2). This was partly because there were no suitable projects running in the core cities (The Hague and Mannheim), and partly because the timescales for possible cooperation did not fit in with the project schedules.

Another approach for the recruitment of partners and partner projects was to use the data from the TRANSCEND Deliverable 2.1 “Landscape of security research: CSO Mapping, Strategies, and Best Practices for Citizen and Societal Engagement” (Martins *et al.*, 2023). In addition, thematically suitable projects were researched via the funding database at the German national level.³ This type of project screening ultimately made it possible to select a total of three projects that were willing to collaborate.

³ <https://www.foerderdatenbank.de/>

Partner Projects of the TRANSCEND Cybersecurity Pilot			
Project	ALIGNER	CYLENCE	PAROMA-MED
Purpose	The ALIGNER (EU-funded) project had the goal to unite European actors who have concerns about AI, law enforcement, and policing to jointly identify and discuss how to enhance Europe’s security whereby AI strengthens law enforcement agencies while providing benefits to the public ⁴ .	The aim of the (German) BMBF-funded project CYLENCE is to develop strategies and tools for the cross-media reporting, detection, and treatment of cyberbullying and hate speech. To this end, organisational strategies and tools for the collection and analysis of (partially) public social data sources (e.g., Facebook, Telegram, Twitter) are to enable investigative and law enforcement authorities (ESBs) to improve the early detection and treatment of cyber abuse cases based on a participatory development process.	The PAROMA-MED project (EU funded) develops, validates, and evaluates a platform-based hybrid-cloud delivery framework for privacy- and security-assured services and applications in federative cross-border environments. For this purpose, the project will develop new architectures, technologies, tools. ⁵
Co-operating Institutions	Fraunhofer Institute for Intelligent Analysis and Information Systems (IAIS)	Technical University Darmstadt (Germany), PEASEC (Science and Technology for Peace and Security)	Qualtek (Athens, Greece), Eurescom (Heidelberg, Germany)

Table 3-1: Overview - Cybersecurity Pilot Collaboration

⁴ <https://aligner-h2020.eu/>; <https://doi.org/10.3030/101020574>

⁵ <https://paroma-med.eu/about/concept-approach/>; <https://doi.org/10.3030/101070222>

The contact and subsequent cooperation with these three projects were successful because all of them were at a point in their development where a workshop and the integration of citizens' perspectives were considered useful. In addition, it was clear from the beginning that TRANSCEND's pilot activity could deliver added value to their technical solution or methodical challenges for the projects, specifically a systematic approach in bringing diverse perspectives to their case.

In most cases, the topic dealt with in the pilot activities was defined by the focus or question of the partner project. Nevertheless, it was possible to organise three very different engagement formats. The main differences lay in the thematic focus, the project objectives, and the way in which the workshop was organised. The topic of the pilot activities was closely linked to the technology discussed in the field. Below we provide an overview of what the topic and the respective technological focus of the various workshops on cybersecurity were. This illustrates that we were able to test and validate different aspects of cybersecurity as well as different methods of citizen participation.

The **Artificial Intelligence Roadmap for Policing and Law Enforcement (ALIGNER)** project, funded by the European Commission, aims to connect European stakeholders who have reservations about the usage of Artificial Intelligence (AI) by law enforcement authorities. Together, they discussed ways in which the use of AI can improve security in Europe while increasing the effectiveness of law enforcement agencies and generating benefits for the public. The project has developed a roadmap for research and policy in AI and security. The aim of the workshop was to familiarise participants with the TRANSCEND approach, which enables meaningful participation of civil society in the development and deployment of security research and technologies.

- Cybersecurity Focus: Cybersecurity policies on national security⁶
- Technology Focus: Artificial Intelligence
- Vision of the Cooperation: Sensibilisation of experts for integrating citizens perspectives, promoting TRANSCEND in the European Cybersecurity Network

The **Detection of Cyberbullying and Hate Speech (CYLENCE)** project deals with the spread of hate speech and cyberbullying via social media. Cyberbullying refers to insulting, exposing and harassing individuals online, while hate messages are directed at specific groups of people. In this context, CYLENCE aims to develop strategies and tools for reporting, recognising and combating cyberbullying and hate messages across all media. The focus of the TRANSCEND-CYLENCE cooperation was on the development of

⁶ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/cybersecurity-policies>

a technical solution that supports the detection and reporting of cyberbullying and hate messages, for example, through a browser extension (cf. Kaufhold *et al.*, 2023).

- Cybersecurity Focus: Awareness raising and combating Hate Speech and Hate Crime⁷
- Technology Focus: Data-driven innovation/Browser extension
- Vision of the Cooperation: Awareness raising & technology improvement

The **PAROMA-MED** project is developing a platform-based hybrid cloud delivery system that aims to fundamentally change the way healthcare data is managed and secured. To address the complex challenges in the medical and healthcare sector, PAROMA-MEDs aim is to empower healthcare providers, professionals, and organisations with a comprehensive solution that enables seamless data flow in federated cross-border environments, with data privacy and security (Ertl and Covaci, 2023, p. 10). The aim of the collaboration was to incorporate the perspectives from citizens in the improvement of the technical solution. Cloud platforms provide the infrastructure and services that enable data to be stored, processed, and presented. The PAROMA-MED dashboards use these resources to give users an overview of personal and medical-related data that should be shared and enable the intersubjective authorisation decision.

- Cybersecurity Focus: Cybersecurity in healthcare⁸
- Technology: Data-driven innovation/Dashboard and cloud-platform
- Vision of the Cooperation: Awareness raising & technology improvement

Against this background, the next section describes the methods selected from the TRANSCEND Toolbox and the concrete implementation of the pilot activities (workshops).

3.2 Method selection

The question of which method to choose depends largely on which question is to be answered in the pilot project and which problem is to be better understood. To find the appropriate method for a pilot activity, the aim of the workshop must first be defined. In all three cases, this was based on the knowledge interest of the partner project and that of TRANSCEND. This clear purpose of the joint activity can be answered at the beginning of the collaboration with the questions *Why do you want to collaborate with citizens? Why would you want to protect human rights?* (see Steen, Afghani and Garstka, 2025, p. 11) In addition, aspects such as *expected benefits* for the collaborators as well as the participants in the workshop were always

⁷ https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/policies/justice-and-fundamental-rights/combating-discrimination/racism-and-xenophobia/combating-hate-speech-and-hate-crime_en

⁸ https://commission.europa.eu/cybersecurity-healthcare_en

discussed as a starting point for planning of the CS pilots (see Steen, Afghani and Garstka, 2025, section 3.1). The key question at this point, however, is: Who is the target group of the workshop and how can we reach them?

The CS pilot provided valuable experience on how to recruit citizens, CSOs, and other stakeholders as participants in a targeted and efficient manner. As different as the project contexts of the pilot projects were, so was the approach to selecting participants. The recruitment procedures for the various pilot projects are outlined below (see also Table 3-2).

3.2.1 ALIGNER

The ALIGNER/TRANSCEND pilot was linked to a project-related workshop held on the 14th of May 2024 that dealt with various topics. The participants were recruited via the project coordination and the ALIGNER network so that the TRANSCEND team had no direct influence on the selection of participants. This approach was successful, as the workshop not only had 30 participants but also the right experts for the subject area. With these 30 participants from different EU countries and with different backgrounds (academics, security practitioners, representatives of law enforcement authorities), various aspects of citizen engagement could be discussed.

3.2.2 CYLENCE

The workshop together with the CYLENCE project was carried out on the 8th of October 2024 in close consultation with the project partners and tailored for the target group. This workshop took place as a physical event and for reasons of research efficiency at the location of the task-leading partner in Karlsruhe (Germany). The aim was to include representatives of the group for which the cybersecurity application developed in the CYLENCE project is intended. Although a large proportion of the population is confronted with hate speech, it is particularly younger people who experience violent communication on the internet, especially on social media (Eurobarometer, 2024, p. 50). Accordingly, the recruitment efforts focused on the target group of young persons aged 16 and up.

Initially, recruitment via multipliers was pursued. The approach began with the identification of relevant multipliers, such as associations, experts, educational institutions, or professional associations. A total of 26 relevant institutions in Karlsruhe and the surrounding area were identified and contacted with a letter and the invitation as well as a request to distribute the workshop invitation to potentially interested citizens. Most institutions and experts dealing with cybersecurity, cyberbullying, citizen science, digital society or media literacy responded very positively to the request and, according to their own statements, distributed the invitation via social media channels, newsletters, mailing lists, or posters in their buildings. In addition, the invitation was distributed via the TRANSCEND Network on LinkedIn and through support of the booked event location. However, we did not

receive a single registration in this way. Still, the advertising was not pointless, as it led to contact being made with a local secondary school. An interested teacher approached the Fraunhofer team and asked whether the workshop could also be organised for her class (secondary level II, age 17-18). This was a good opportunity to hold the pilot workshop in person with a very suitable target group.

3.2.3 PAROMA-MED

When planning the collaboration with PAROMA-MED, it quickly became clear that the 29th of January 2025 workshop had to be held in English and online because of the international composition of the PAROMA-MED consortium. The participant target group was deliberately loosely defined, as the organisers agreed that the topic of cybersecurity in the medical field could be relevant for a wide range of stakeholders with different backgrounds. In terms of recruitment, it was decided to contact TRANSCEND and PAROMA-MED's extended networks. Contacts were sought for people and institutions from the healthcare sector, the data economy and medical technology. Contacts were invited to take part in the workshop and forward the invitation. In addition, the event was advertised via LinkedIn. Participants were able to register for the workshop via a dedicated landing page. These efforts resulted in a total of 15 registrations from people from different backgrounds.

Pilot Partner Project	Recruitment	Reflection
ALIGNER	Direct: Project Partner Network	Successful, high commitment because of project connection
CYLENCE	Indirect: via Multipliers and LinkedIn	Unsuccessful, high uncertainty, no registrations
PAROMA-MED	Direct: via own and Partner Network Indirect: via Multipliers and LinkedIn	Successful, personal approach works the real outcome of indirect access cannot be measured

Table 3-22: Reflection on Recruitment Strategies for Pilot Attendees

3.3 Implementation

The pilot's environment is just as important as the recruitment strategy. The cybersecurity pilot consisted of two online workshops. It should be noted that online environments are more flexible and, above all, open; theoretically, as the number of participants is not limited. In our experience, the duration is particularly important for online meetings. They must be shorter and as interesting and interactive as possible to keep the participants' attention. The best way to do this is to look for a video conferencing platform that facilitates this and is technically stable. In the workshop with

ALIGNER, we also worked with the Conceptboard system to enable interaction. This proved to be complicated because not all participants could access the platform, and many were not familiar with its functionality. In our third case we discussed the technical solution developed by PAROMA-MED as part of the online workshop. Here too, access was not entirely straightforward. These two examples show that unexpected difficulties can always arise despite the good preparation of the workshop procedures and the testing of possible demos.

On the other hand, online workshops create a certain anonymity, making it easier for participants to remain invisible. We therefore insisted on holding a face-to-face meeting for a sensitive and sometimes upsetting topic such as hate speech and bullying. The conditions for our CYLENCE workshop were set by the environment of our group of participants: a classroom and a duration of 90 minutes. It was helpful for the discussion that the classroom was a familiar environment for our participants, in which also all the technical equipment were available.

The methods used to implement the pilots were as diverse as the pilots themselves. The Toolbox offers starting points and specific information for various issues but still leaves enough room for creativity resulting from the cooperation with the project partners. At the beginning of the planning phase of the pilot activities, a workshop planning sheet was drawn up with all partners. This not only served as an overview of the objectives and tasks but also enabled constant monitoring of the progress of the work (see also Toolbox, Section 3.3). The methodological setting of the three pilots is explained and reflected in more detail below.

3.3.1 ALIGNER

The aim of the joint workshop was to find out what can be learned from the experiences of the experts present and what the general challenges are when integrating citizens into security research. In addition, we wanted to make the project more visible to the relevant target group and thus facilitate future collaborations. The event took place online on the 13th of May 2024 with around 30 participants. By integrating the TRANSCEND pilot activity into the agenda of a regular ALIGNER project event, there was a clear timeframe and objective for the workshop (see Section 3.1). The structure of the 90-minute workshop was as follows:

1. Open discussion using pre-formulated questions to explore knowledge and ideas (World Café):
 - What experiences have been made in the ALIGNER project with the integration of citizens in security research? What can be learned from this?
 - What role does technical complexity play in the integration of citizens?
 - What added value can/could ALIGNER generate for the public?
 - What role did the citizens' perspective play in ALIGNER?

To facilitate the dialogue with a large and diverse group and to explore different perspectives and ideas, we chose the World Café method from the Toolbox. In contrast to a 'real' World Café, there were no table changes or breakout sessions; instead, the questions were discussed with everyone in the spirit of an open World Café. The participants were able to take part in the discussion verbally or non-verbally via a prepared concept board. The advantages of the method can be summarised as follows:

- Diversity of perspectives: The participation of different people makes it possible to gather different views and ideas, leading to innovative solutions.
- Visual documentation: Results of discussions were recorded visually (e.g. on large sheets of paper or, as in this case, on an online concept board), which increases the visibility of ideas and enables shared documentation.
- Collective knowledge: The method enables collective knowledge to be used and integrated, maximising the intelligence of the group.

2. Discussion on challenges (Deliberative Workshop)

The deliberative workshop was chosen as the next agenda item, to consider the challenges of integrating citizens' perspectives in the development of technology and research into security solutions (see Steen, Afghani and Garstka, 2025 section 5.3). The discussion was structured using problem-centred questions to encourage participants to think critically about the topics and take different points of view into account. Here, a concept board was used to collect and visualise ideas from the participants, too. Questions included inter alia:

- Where were/are challenges seen in the integration of citizens' perspectives?
- What ethical challenges exist in connection with the topics of discrimination, transparency, trust in the AI decision-making process (ALIGNER focus)

3. Input on TRANSCEND (10 minutes)

Finally, we presented TRANSCEND's overall objective and approach, making the project more visible to European stakeholders. Following the workshop, two contacts were made with people working on similar topics. They were invited to join the TRANSCEND Network on LinkedIn to follow the activities and continue to actively participate in the discussions. Topics included:

- What TRANSCEND's Toolbox can do
- Offer for networking
- Open points

3.3.2 CYLENCE

The purpose of the CYLENCE pilot project was derived from the aim of the project, in which values and value conflicts are of particular interest as an empirical result that is relevant from a civil society perspective in the context of developing and applying artificial intelligence to detect and evaluate hate speech, and from which requirements and implications for the design of technology shall be derived. The following overarching question was discussed in the workshop:

What social challenges, conflicts of values, and socio-technical solutions are emerging in the field of civil cybersecurity research regarding the development of artificial intelligence to detect abusive content?

The pilot took place on the 8th of October 2025 as a 90-minute in-person workshop with 16 participants. The workshop had four distinct sections; each designed with different methodological approaches. For example, the opening consisted of an introduction and a video as an icebreaker. The discussion about the technical solution began with a deliberative workshop to capture the perspectives and to better understand and improve the technical solution from the citizens' point of view. In the third part of the workshop, focus groups were formed to identify the challenges and opportunities of the presented technology solution (Steen, Afghani and Garstka, 2025, Sect. 5.8). Secondly, a future scenario was outlined by looking into the future and asking how the students imagine technological development in the future. In a final discussion, everything was summarised and remaining open questions were clarified. The table below shows the workshop joint planning.

Phase	GOAL CYLENCE	GOAL TRANSCEND	Methods/Toolbox Usage
1. Opening	Raising awareness of the problem of hate speech, distribution of project-related input for discussion	Brief introduction, explorative approach to the topic	<p>Short introduction and impulse:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Information material/glossary Name and statement of the participants: What do you think the consequences of hate speech can be for individuals, but also for whole groups? <p>OR</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> What do you think can be done to prevent hate speech or mitigate its consequences? Video on the topic
2. Discussion	Presentation and discussion of the development status of the project's technical solutions: browser extension (preferably live or at concept level)	When exploring a socio-technical solution using an application-oriented example, predefined focal points/questions are discussed after the participants' initial "free" impressions.	<p>Presentation of the technical solution (CYLENCE), followed by a discussion in the smaller (focus) groups</p> <p>Perspective workshop on technology</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Browser plugin: either a demonstrator from an ongoing thesis or a mock-up from our application partner Guided discussion based on questions about the demonstrator: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Looking at the dashboard or programs again now, do you have any unanswered questions about them? What else do you think of the apps? What is your impression? Do you think they are well or poorly implemented?

Phase	GOAL CYLENCE	GOAL TRANSCEND	Methods/Toolbox Usage
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Would you use such an app or not? Why? What could be improved?
3. Synthesis of the socio-technical perspective	Discussion of values and value conflicts based on the "AI case study" on recognizing and evaluating hate speech	Following the discussion on the technical solution, a scenario such as that of AI can be discussed - proximity to the application would be important.	<p>Discussion of possible technical solutions and future scenarios.</p> <p>Focus groups</p> <p>1. Consequences</p> <p>The participants discuss the possible consequences of the technology</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What problems and opportunities do you see in dealing with hate speech and cyberbullying with AI? <p>2. Future Scenario</p> <p>Participants try to develop a vision of the future, to draw a picture of future possibilities.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What would you like to see in the use of technology to counter hate speech?
4. Conclusion/ Evaluation	Values and value conflicts, which are relevant from a citizen perspective	Evaluation of the method(s), feasibility and results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Final discussion (1. content: what still needs to be said and 2. organization: what was bad, what was good)

Table 3-33: Workshop Planning between CYLENCE and TRANSCEND

3.3.3 PAROMA-MED

The joint PAROMA-MED and TRANSCEND workshop aimed to educate participants on critical issues of collecting and analysing medical data and enhance their skills in understanding challenges and opportunities of digital solutions. This was substantiated in a discussion about the dashboard developed in PAROMA-MED, which gives data subjects an overview of the medical data stored about them and enables them to give (or revoke) consent for its use. A combination of expert contributions and interactive discussions led to a lively discussion. With the help of the deliberative workshop and the participatory design/human-centred design approaches from the Toolbox, it was possible to identify crucial aspects from a citizen's perspective. The workshop was conducted online for 90 minutes on the 29th of January 2025.

The agenda in the following box describes the structure of the workshop. With a complex topic such as the exchange of medical data and the value of patient data, it was very useful to get expert input, after which the dashboard was presented. All participants were able to explore the dashboard for themselves.

Agenda of the workshop together with PAROMA-MED

1. Welcome!
2. Citizens Perspectives for PAROMA-MED Solution
3. Discussing GDPR awareness & AI dependencies
4. Reflection on Platform
5. Summary & Evaluation

Textbox 3-1: Agenda of the workshop with PAROMA-MED

Specific questions about technical solutions were then asked as part of the participatory design/human-centred design approach. There were three phases here, the criticism phase in which possible problems were raised. This was followed by the fantasy phase, in which the solutions to the platform were suggested and discussed, and the implementation phase, i.e. a discussion about specific next steps required for the ideas from the fantasy phase to be implemented. All phases were guided by pre-formulated questions. The workshop was then concluded with a short summary.

The following table provides an evaluative comparison of the methods tested in all three cybersecurity pilots.

Method	Interest in Knowledge in Cybersecurity Pilots
World Café	Open-ended questions that encourage diverse perspectives and knowledge
Deliberative Workshop	Structured sequence of a discussion in relation to a complex topic

Perspective Workshop	Exploring Challenges and Benefits from a particular Technology
Focus Group	Problem-centred discussion focusing on the citizens' view of an evolving issue
Participatory Design/ Human-centred Design Approach	Discussion between developers and users to improve development of a specific technology

Table 3-44: Comparison of tested Methods in the Cybersecurity Pilots

3.4 Feedback from the pilot workshops

In terms of feedback on the methods described in the Toolbox, it can be stated that all methods were perceived as suitable for the Cybersecurity pilot's goals. What is crucial is how the methods are coordinated and brought to life. To reflect on the Toolbox and the workshop overall from the perspective of citizens and participants in the pilot activities, either an open feedback session (ALIGNER) was held after the workshops or feedback questionnaires (CYLENCE and PAROMA-MED) were distributed. These feedback forms were formulated in cooperation with the project partners and distributed in paper form (CYLENCE) or online (PAROMA-MED).

3.4.1 ALIGNER and PAROMA-MED Feedback

No comments on the workshop (see internal reflection section 3.4) and no feedback on the survey (see internal reflection section 3.4).

3.4.2 CYLENCE Feedback

Category	What do you think was good?	What do you find worth optimising?
Workshop (Methods)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussion phase • Prototype Presentation • Various chances to participate • Input and individual point of view were valued • Able to take notes all the time • Room for a lot of questions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussion phase too long • Not trying the prototype • Big group/circle not as good as the focus group • More time to think about questions and talk about it with a partner
Content	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explanation of the topic • Good answers to questions • Clear structure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easier wording • Being more specific on the issue, not that general

<p>Prototype</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Good solution. I will use it • Good idea 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve the design; make it more colourful • Use it on phones not only on computers
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Table 3-55: Participants Feedback on the CYLENCE Workshop

The students' feedback from the CYLENCE workshop was directly incorporated into the development of the next version of the Toolbox.

Workshop/Methods:

- Space and time for thoughts: Deliberative workshops in the cybersecurity field need clear guiding questions. However, it can be helpful to leave additional time for reflecting the questions with the participants. Unfortunately, we did not have this time in the limited 90 minutes.
- Be flexible: You should be flexible enough that you can easily adapt the questions if the participants have certain priorities.

Technology/Prototype:

- Practical test setting: Technology should not only be discussed in a participatory way, but should be made accessible; a setting should be created to allow participants to test the prototype themselves
- Structured testing: Create a structured setting which gives room for personal experimentation but also for joint reflection.

Outcome:

- Know your field: The young target group is deeply involved in the topic—be well prepared for such a discussion.
- Non-verbal outcomes: Do not underestimate the importance of participants (handwritten) notes taken during the discussion.

3.5 Findings from the Cybersecurity Pilot

In addition to the methodological validation of the workshop to further improve the Toolbox, the participants' personal concerns and thoughts on security technologies will also be reflected so that knowledge about the field of cybersecurity can be improved as an outcome of the workshops. As described in section 3.1 of this report, the three pilot projects differ greatly in terms of topics. This illustrates the diversity of the workshops held. The results of the pilot projects are discussed in more detail below.

3.5.1 ALIGNER

- Cybersecurity Focus: Cybersecurity Policies on national security⁹
- Technology: Artificial Intelligence

⁹ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/cybersecurity-policies>

Challenges in engaging citizens in research and deployment	Explanation
	<p>these systems. Citizens may not have the technical knowledge to contribute effectively.</p> <p>As it is a black box technology, it is difficult even for experts to explain why an AI makes certain decisions and what the determining factors are.</p>
Lack of resources	Time and financial resources are needed to effectively engage citizens.
Generate interest for the topic	It is a challenge to spark citizens' interest and mobilise them to participate.
Language and other barriers	For most tasks and activities, it is difficult to involve citizens in security projects due to the sensitivity and/or confidentiality of the findings.
Unclear effectiveness	An effective and inclusive engagement of citizens requires careful planning and resources. It is also necessary to define what effectiveness means for the project.

Table 3-66: Challenges in the integration of citizens in AI development projects

3.5.2 CYLENCE

- Cybersecurity Focus: hate speech and hate crime¹⁰
- Technology: Data-driven innovation, browser extension
- Vision of the cooperation: Awareness Raising & Technology improvement

The workshop started with the general questions: *What do you think can be done to prevent hate speech and cyber mobbing or mitigate its consequences?* Participants discussed different approaches to tackling cyberbullying and hate speech, particularly on social media. Statements were made on the following aspects:

- Early education: Participants agreed that children should learn empathy and how to use social media from an early age to reduce hate behaviour.
- Stricter rules for social media: Many participants argued for stricter policies against bullying and hate speech, including better enforcement of existing policies.
- Awareness of consequences: It was suggested that users should be made aware of the consequences of their postings and comments and

¹⁰ https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/policies/justice-and-fundamental-rights/combating-discrimination/racism-and-xenophobia/combating-hate-speech-and-hate-crime_en

that platforms such as Instagram should potentially block the profiles of people who post hate comments.

- Anonymity: Participants suggested limiting anonymity on social media to reduce the spread of hate comments.
- Workshops and education: The idea of workshops in schools or kindergartens was mentioned to raise early awareness of cyberbullying.

Overall, the focus was on a combination of education, stricter rules, and the promotion of respectful behaviour in digital and cyberspace. The technical solution, the browser extension, was then discussed.

Students discussed a prototype tool for detecting hate comments on social media - in the case of Instagram. Some people use Instagram mainly through the app, which could limit the practicality of the tool, so development for mobile applications is suggested. The tool only scans social media content to identify potential hate speech. It is currently in the research phase and not in use. The PEASEC team admitted that the tool does not yet work optimally, as the AI used was not specifically designed for this application. Future developments could focus on detecting criminally relevant hate speech. Participants found the tool useful in making it easier to report hate speech, which could lead to increased reporting of such content. Some express concerns that the tool could focus too much on hate comments but also see the benefit of becoming more aware of the issue. Participants were interested in using the tool, especially for controversial topics, and see it as helpful in tackling hate speech. Overall, the tool was considered to be practicable and potentially effective, although it is still under development.

This was followed by a discussion on values and value conflicts, based on the "AI case study" on hate speech detection and assessment (see also section 3.2). The discussion focused on trust in AI systems for detecting hate speech on social media. In summary, the discussion showed that there is both trust and scepticism towards AI. Participants expressed concerns about the reliability of AI, as detecting hate speech is complex and often requires personal judgment. Many have used AI for various applications in the past and found that it sometimes makes mistakes, which affects trust. It was pointed out that the use of such tools could influence user behaviour, as more time is spent reading comments, which can reduce the enjoyment of social media.

Participants emphasised the importance of personal morality and suggested the development of additional tools to report comments that are not detected by AI. Technical challenges, such as detecting mis-coded hate comments, were also raised. Participants agreed that continuous improvement of AI is needed to detect new forms of expression. Suggestions included the possibility of integrating user feedback to improve hate speech detection. Overall, the discussion showed mixed confidence in AI systems. Participants would like to see better interaction between AI and users to improve hate speech detection and avoid misinterpretation.

Values and conflicts	Description
Trust vs. scepticism	Users are unsure whether they can trust the AI, as it may not have the same moral standards as they do.
Freedom of expression vs. protection against hate speech	There is a tension between protecting freedom of expression and the need to act against hate speech.
Individual perception vs. algorithmic decisions	Users could perceive comments as hate speech that are not recognised as such by the AI, leading to conflicts in decision-making.
Ethical responsibility vs. technological dependency	The responsibility to report hate speech could lead users to rely more on the tool, while at the same time they have an ethical responsibility to judge for themselves what constitutes hate speech.
Privacy vs. surveillance	Using AI to monitor comments could raise privacy and surveillance concerns.

Table 3-77: Values and Value Conflicts in using AI for Hate Speech Detection

3.5.3 PAROMA-MED

- Cybersecurity focus: Cybersecurity in healthcare¹¹
- Technology: Data-driven innovation; dashboard and cloud-Platform
- Vision of the cooperation: Awareness raising & technology improvement

The workshop was started with the icebreaker question: *What concerns and problems arise when sharing medical data?* Such a question-based start proved successful and allowed for a quick transition to the topic of the pilot. The following aspects were mentioned by the participants:

- Patient autonomy: The ability for patients to make their own decisions about their health information is central to modern healthcare. This promotes a sense of control and empowerment.
- Control of their own data: Patients must be able to decide how their data is used to build trust in the healthcare system. Transparent handling of personal data increases the acceptance of data sharing.
- Challenges:
 - Data leakage: The security of healthcare data is critical. Data leaks can lead to misuse and loss of trust.
 - Inaccurate information: Incorrect or inaccurate data can lead to incorrect diagnoses or treatments, jeopardising patient safety.
- Transparency: To increase patient trust, it is important to be transparent about what data is being shared and for what purpose. Open information about data handling is essential.

¹¹ https://commission.europa.eu/cybersecurity-healthcare_en

- Extent and purpose of data sharing: Patients should be clearly informed about the extent to which their data will be shared and the purposes, whether for research, treatment, or other purposes.
- Different terminologies: Different terms and definitions related to data sharing can lead to misunderstandings. These differences need to be addressed to ensure clear communication.
- Consistent terms and standards: Establishing consistent terminology and standards when exchanging data can improve efficiency and comprehension, ultimately leading to better collaboration between patients and healthcare providers.

After the expert input on GDPR compliance in the PAROMA-MED platform, the next part of the workshop focused on the simulation of the dashboard being developed in PAROMA-MED. This was presented by the developer, and all participants were able to try out the dashboard. This also addressed a point of criticism from the CYLENCE workshop, where participants would have liked to discover the technical solution themselves. Several important aspects of the technical improvement of the dashboard were discussed by the participants. The dashboard was discussed (according to the participatory/human-centred centred design approach) along three questions: (1) Critique, in which participants talk about current experiences and problems; (2) Fantasy, in which they explore and imagine possible solutions; and (3) Implementation, in which they plan concrete actions for the immediate future (see Toolbox, section 5.5).

1. Critique Phase

The critique phase describes the general aspects that emerged during the dashboard simulation:

- *Interoperability*: There are significant challenges in exchanging data between different systems, which hinders the seamless integration of the platform.
- *Data formats*: Unclear or inconsistent data formats can lead to confusion and misunderstanding, making the dashboard difficult to use.
- *Knowledge gaps*: Differences in users' knowledge and technical skills could lead to unequal use of the dashboard, putting some users at a disadvantage.
- *Unclear target group*: It is unclear for which specific audience the dashboard has been developed, which calls into question the relevance and effectiveness of the tool.

The fantasy and implementation phases can be compared in terms of their content; they served our project partner PAROM-MED as important pointers and guidelines for the further development of the dashboard.

2. Fantasy Phase	3. Implementation Phase
Clarity about functionality and comprehensive information about data and its processing	Comprehensive guidance: Provide a clear and easily accessible guide or tutorial that explains the dashboard features in detail.
Full information about the data and how it is processed	Better information about data: Providing information about the sources of the data and their reliability to increase confidence in the data.
Improve usability	Intuitive user interface: Design an easy-to-use and intuitive interface that allows users to navigate quickly and efficiently
	Visualisations and analytics: Integrating data visualisations that make information easier to understand and analytics that help users better interpret the data
Profile of User is missing	Personalisation: Ability to customise the dashboard so that users can quickly reach frequently used functions or data views.

Table 3-88: Aspects on Technology Improvement of the PAROMA-MED Dashboard

3.6 Summary and outlook

The previous sections have described not only the extent to which the Toolbox has been improved by the knowledge gained from the pilot workshops but also the feedback about the workshops themselves. In the following, we will reflect on the activities of the CS pilot. This concerns both the organisation and the implementation of the workshops.

The search for partner projects took much longer than originally expected, which should be considered, as it is not easy to make contacts and organise joint activities without an existing network. Nevertheless, all the workshops went smoothly, and the teamwork between the project partners and TRANSCEND was excellent.

ALIGNER

- Organisation
 - Perfect teamwork in terms of reliability, communication, results orientation with project partner
 - Open communication about expectations and joint objectives (see Chapter 3.3.2) was key
- Methods

- Using a digital tool for collaborative work is always a challenge - not all participants had access to the tool, so consideration needs to be given to using it in future workshops
- Engaging people in online discussions is always difficult; increased activation of participants should be reflected in the Toolbox without forcing people.

CYLENCE

- Organisation
 - Perfect teamwork in terms of reliability, communication, results orientation with project partner
 - Open communication about expectations was key
 - Setting concrete goals at the start of planning is key
 - Planning face-to-face workshops is time-consuming; you need someone to take the lead and coordinate all communication and tasks.
 - Recruiting citizens is a challenging task; it takes time and the right contacts (see also Section 3.1).
- Methods
 - For sensitive and complex topics, it makes sense to consider methodical options such as time for individual reflection and/or partner work

PAROMA-MED

- Organisation
 - Perfect teamwork in terms of reliability, communication, results orientation with project partner
 - Open communication about expectations (see Chapter 3.3.3) was key
 - It can take a long time for projects to synchronise and for the technical solution to be sufficiently presentable, and this must be considered when planning a workshop
- Methods
 - Getting people to participate in online discussions is always difficult, so the Toolbox could consider how to incentivise participants to be more active.

The results presented show that working with experts and citizens in research can contribute to making cybersecurity solutions more effective, fairer, and application oriented. To address the challenges of involving citizens in cybersecurity identified in Chapter 3.1, the following approaches were developed during the workshops: Education and advocacy to raise awareness of cybersecurity risks and their importance. The provision of easily understandable and accessible information material based on the current state of research and the active involvement of citizens in the development process of cybersecurity solutions.

Reflecting on this in the context of using the TRANSCEND Toolbox, it can be said that this document should contain several essential aspects. Firstly, it should offer a variety of methodologies suitable for different situations and audiences to meet different cybersecurity contexts. Ease of use for different actors is also crucial; the Toolbox should contain clear and understandable instructions that make it easy for users to quickly grasp and apply the methods.

Flexibility is another important point: The methods should be adaptable so that they can be adapted by actors to different contexts, issues and target groups (see Section 3.2). The timing of the Toolbox design and development should include opportunities for evaluation and feedback to enable continuous improvement. It was useful to be able to incorporate findings and reflections into the new version of the Toolbox after each pilot activity.

Given the target audience of citizens, it was not possible to run all three workshops with citizens completely without a background in cybersecurity. This can be seen as a clear limitation.

Finally, it was not only possible to connect the networks of the project partners with the TRANSCEND network but also to plan joint activities such as blog posts for the TRANSCEND Blog (e.g. Blogpost on joint workshop with PAROMA-MED, see Runge and Mohnani, 2025). The planning and implementation of the workshops resulted in valuable collaborations that should continue beyond the end of the project. What is special about this is that the socio-technical approach can be followed, and cybersecurity can be considered not only in a social participative sense but also in a technological development sense.

4 Pilot on Disaster Resilient Societies (DRS)

4.1 Organisation of the pilot activities

Society is facing many risks simultaneously while society's capacity to pay attention to those risks is declining. Therefore, an 'all-hazards', an 'all-phases', and an "all-of-society" approach is needed to overcome the effects of disasters and crises. While risk assessment, early warning, regulatory measures, and cross-border cooperation are the main domains of public authorities, awareness, preparedness, and response are shared responsibilities within society.

Based on the UN Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR), in June 2023, the EU adopted five new "European Disaster Resilience Goals" to strengthen societal resilience and preparedness and empower citizens. The five main goals are: anticipate, prepare, alert, respond, and secure. Austria has adopted and implemented many DRR principles and measures at all administrative levels, established a national platform for DRR, where the Austrian Red Cross is a partner, and plays an active role in the international community of DRR.

The Austrian Red Cross is both a civil society organisation (with more than 1.1 million members and supporters) and a first and second responder in the public response network of Austrian authorities and therefore a logical link between engaged or affected citizens and public authorities and policy-makers. In 2007, the ARC initiated "*Team Österreich*" together with Ö3 – a radio station of the Austrian public broadcaster ORF – a platform where citizens can engage in responding to disasters. Since that time, *Team Österreich* has become a multifunctional (digital) platform for preparedness (on a household level), early situational awareness (warnings and alerts), training (both online and offline), crowd sourcing and crowd tasking (online assignments, "human sensors"), mobilisation (more than 100,000 members), providing first aid (nationwide automatic dispatch to out-of-hospital cardiac arrests), and disaster relief (thousands of *Team Österreich* members participated in missions after floods in 2012, 2017, and 2024).

4.2 Method selection and Implementation

To promote citizen involvement in disaster resilience, the Austrian Red Cross organised a series of three meetings: focus groups with citizens about a mobile app for disaster resilience; a series of interviews with professionals from another NGO; and an online workshop about the use of technology in disaster resilience, with people from countries around the globe.

Each meeting was purposefully structured to build upon the outcomes of the previous meeting, creating a learning experience.

In the **first meeting**, 16 citizens participated in a workshop. They were recruited and invited through *Team Österreich*, a collaboration between the Austrian Red Cross and the most popular nationwide radio channel, *Hitradio*

Ö3, which enables people to offer and receive mutual help. The mobile app that was discussed has three basic functions: to prepare; to notify (updates on storms, rain, snow, ice, thunderstorms, heat, and civil protection alerts from the government); and to coordinate offering and receiving help. The workshop had three main goals: to discuss disaster preparedness; to discuss the current version of the *Team Österreich* mobile app (Android and iOS) and make suggestions for its further improvement; and to discuss various ethical, human rights, and societal aspects. The workshop took the form of three parallel focus groups, with 5 or 6 persons in each. The average age of participants was 60 years; three participants had a migrant background; and one worked in an organisation that provides care to people with special needs and could bring their perspective to the table. From the workshop came several suggestions to improve the mobile app: e.g., to improve its functions to zoom in and zoom out; and to offer downloadable checklists (PDF). Overall, the participants evaluated the workshop as useful; 14 of 16 indicated that they had been able to express their concerns and needs.

Upon reflection, three suggestions can be made for the improvement of such workshops with citizens: 1) to reflect on the type of people you want to have in your workshop, e.g., recruiting and inviting younger people, either in the same workshop or in an additional workshop; 2) to start the workshop with an activity to 'break the ice' to make people more comfortable speaking up and contributing; this may be especially relevant for people who feel less able to speak up, culture-wise or language-wise; and 3) to make the discussion about ethical, human rights, and societal aspects more practical, e.g., give practical examples of 'non-discrimination' or 'privacy' from daily life experiences.

AutRC organised a **second meeting** to further explore possibilities to engage citizens in disaster resilience and disaster relief operations. This meeting involved three people from the Disaster Aid Department of Caritas (Vienna) and three people from the Austrian Red Cross/*Team Österreich*. Caritas is an NGO that is active in disaster relief, hunger aid, home care for disabled people, shelters for homeless people and single mothers, refugee aid, and occupational projects for unemployed people, among others.

Due to the experience and expertise of the participants, and their small number, the meeting took the form of semi-structured interviews. They discussed the findings of the first workshop and focused on the concerns for privacy (*who can access personal data that people give through the app*), as well as on comparing the average age of mobile app users vis-à-vis the average age of users who are supposed to benefit from the *Team Österreich* app. They also discussed how their organisations can (better) engage citizens in disaster relief operations, how they can use technology to (better) match first responders and volunteers to people in need, and how they and other CSOs can collaborate in initiatives such as *Team Österreich*.

A **third meeting** was organised to further discuss and share experiences about the role of technology in disaster resilience ('From Bytes to Relief'). They collaborated with three experts in organising this meeting: from Code4all ('an international network of civic tech changemakers'); from the EU-funded project vera.ai ('disinformation analysis and AI-supported verification tools and services'); and from a local NGO that works with migrants (to provide a broader perspective on the concerns and needs of vulnerable people).

The meeting was hosted online, and participants were recruited mainly via ReliefWeb, a global platform for humanitarian aid organisations. A total of 29 people participated, many from countries outside the EU, e.g., Nigeria, the Philippines, Pakistan, and Indonesia. The organisers wanted to enable people to participate actively and chose a *Perspective Workshop* format, with a focus on two topics: data protection and privacy, and the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI).

The meeting had the following agenda: 60 minutes of introduction and speakers; 60 minutes of discussion on how to best address citizens' concerns, conclusions and closing, and evaluation. Participants found that the meeting fulfilled their expectations (4.4 on a 5-point scale) and considered the topics relevant and important (4.2 on a 5-point scale).

A fourth and **final meeting** was held with various professionals from the AutRC to discuss and clarify how they can best organise responses to disasters and extreme events in collaboration with the population. They are committed to learning from each other and from practical experiences to further develop and improve a constantly evolving catalogue of good practices and checklists.

From the outset, AutRC assumed the strategic, operational, and administrative leadership of the pilot, ensuring that all activities aligned with TRANSCEND's broader mission to enhance citizen participation in disaster-resilient societies.

The Disaster Resilient Societies (DRS) pilot, with the title "*Humanitarian Disaster Relief and Civil Society Engagement*", was organised by the Austrian Red Cross (AutRC). The objective of this pilot was to shed light on the Red Cross's commitment after disasters and extreme events in and with the population, to further develop it, and to learn from each other and from our experiences. The aim of the pilot was to develop a constantly evolving catalogue and concept of good practices, checklists, support formats, and action lists.

An invitation to the pilot was sent to all regional branches, requesting 1-3 participants who ideally (together) covered the following profile:

- *Team Österreich* supervisors (regional level)
- Local commanders & decision-makers
- Voluntary social workers
- Disaster relief workers

The 2-day DRS pilot workshop, from noon to noon, in person, had a total of 22 attendants from the regional branches of Vienna, Burgenland, Lower Austria, Upper Austria, Carinthia, Styria, Tirol, and HQ Vienna. It took place on the 6th and 7th of November 2024, at the Hotel Novotel, Wien. The participants were travelling from all parts of Austria; we wanted to create a very welcoming environment. The hotel was very close to the train station, so everyone had a chance to reach the meeting room directly after arrival, and they could stay overnight in the same hotel. After the first day of the workshop, AutRC organised dinner for all participants in a nearby restaurant.

AutRC adopted a participatory design combining focus groups, the World Café, and storytelling. These methods were selected based on the TRANSCEND Toolbox's recommendations and were adapted to first responders and expert settings in collaboration with all practitioners and locals working with citizens, especially after disasters.

4.3 Results of the pilot workshop

In view of climate change and the increase in disasters, we need resilient societies. We can achieve this not only by strengthening emergency and aid organisations, such as the Austrian Red Cross, but above all through the active participation of civil society—in preparation, in the event of an emergency, or in reconstruction. The TRANSCEND project plays a crucial role in this by developing and implementing innovative approaches that promote the participation of civil society and thus strengthen resilience to disasters.

The **results** of the workshops could be formulated as follows:

- Engage *Team Österreich* members in small-scale events on a regular basis:
 - Alternatively, inform them actively when their efforts are not needed.
- Be ready to welcome spontaneous volunteers:
 - Establish ad hoc volunteer reception processes.
 - Adapt statutes to involve citizens as members of the association.
- Keep working on a vulnerability analysis: where affected persons need help and support the most after incidents and disasters.
- Keep working on a Toolbox (assessment tools, a “menu” of offered services, communication channels to affected persons, etc.).
- Engage with mayors and social workers at the community level to help identify the most vulnerable households (on a regular basis and in times of disasters).
- Adapt and improve our *Team Österreich App* – include a module (besides alerts, prevention and preparedness, missions, online missions) to foster immediate financial aid for affected households after disasters.

The citizens' main **feedback** about the technology could be summarised as follows:

- Citizens trust that the Austrian Red Cross complies with all relevant laws and regulations (e.g. data protection, privacy).
- Citizens expect that they will be engaged (informed, alerted) once a situation occurs where they have the impression (mostly driven by media) that their help could be needed (relevance of the system).
- Citizens challenge us when information given in the system is faulty (accuracy).
- Citizens want to choose the level of interaction that will take place with them (possibility to configure the system based on their needs and preferences).
- Citizens expect the system to work 24/7/365 without major interruptions (availability) on the devices they are using (platform independence).
- Citizens expect to have the choice of whether to participate in a mission/task or not (voluntary service).
- Citizens trust that – when engaged in a mission – they will be led by professionals and embedded in a system where their safety and well-being are guaranteed and assured (welfare and insurance).

4.4 Lessons learnt

1. Lack of uptake of the *Team Österreich* by CSOs

Professional responders need public (financial) resources to establish and maintain their services. In return, their promise is to always stand by citizens in need. This relationship, however, fosters a culture of dependency among citizens, on the one hand and a strong tendency for professional responders to want to fulfil this promise, on the other. It is an exclusive approach to disaster response because asking for help (e.g., from engaged citizens or international aid) could be seen as a breach of that promise. To mitigate this challenge, the Austrian Red Cross is committed to working with other relevant professional responders. The fire brigade, police, public authorities, and army help to overcome this dilemma and establish a disaster relief culture where cooperation across organisational domains is a major asset and is included in communication strategies. This should not only lead to an increase in *Team Österreich* missions in cooperation with other first and second responders and civil society but also to a new conceptual approach to strengthening societal resilience and reducing citizens' dependency on state efforts. We have seen that citizens – especially those organised and prepared like *Team Österreich* – are willing to help and assist their fellow citizens and professional responders to a greater extent than the professional responders demand their help. Once citizens who are ready to help are included in the “public response” more frequently, professional responders will be more comfortable with this form of engagement, and a mutual benefit will be gained.

2. Lack of preparedness by individuals at the household level

Citizens and their households are underprepared for situations of crisis and disaster. Enhancing this preparedness is not just beneficial for the individual and their family but also for their employer (as it increases the probability

that individuals can attend to their work), professional responders (as it reduces their workload), the community (as it frees up citizens to be an available resource to help others), and for society as a whole (as it massively increases resilience, reducing economic and other losses). Regulations and marketing campaigns have proven effective at encouraging consumers to invest in passive safety. For example, most European citizens would not buy a car without airbags, something that was commonplace in previous decades. To help citizens better prepare for crises and disasters, a similar campaign for public awareness (action- and lifestyle-oriented) is recommended, alongside supporting regulations by lawmakers driven by the government. For example, including support for household preparedness of employees of critical infrastructure providers (CIPs) in the directive on the resilience of critical entities would lead to a focus on the preparedness of human resources in CIPs. The willingness to work in times of disaster is highly dependent on the situation of one's household.

As long as employees are busy restoring an acceptable situation for their families after being affected by a disaster, they are not ready and willing to work. A better level of preparedness in crucial employees' households reduces the stress of restoring a safe and sound environment for their families and therefore increases the workforce for CIPs when needed the most. The campaign should therefore be aimed at preparing households, with a focus on the households of public authority and critical infrastructure providers' employees. Elevating the awareness of Austrian citizens concerning their household preparedness will further filter through to the research arena. This allows for more immediate connections to be made in terms of the relevance of the research and its impact on the citizen.

3. Need for greater collaboration between existing disaster preparedness technologies and citizen-focused research projects

Citizen science is a methodology to engage citizens in scientific research by enabling them to contribute data, information, and knowledge in a structured way. Such approaches are used in the digital missions of *Team Österreich*, where citizen participants (of the app) are asked to contribute to a situational overview by sharing information (text, images, sensor information) or to perform specific tasks (dissemination, helping neighbours, online tasks). The synergies with citizen science research projects are evident: both target groups are similar, the learning-by-doing effect is significant, and cooperation will be of mutual benefit. The Austrian Red Cross is committed to developing further concepts to interlink the two fields of community work by increasing the participation of existing disaster preparedness technologies in citizen science research projects.

4.5 Summary and Outlook

The Disaster Resilient Societies pilot, led by the Austrian Red Cross, highlights the importance of engaging citizens in disaster resilience through inclusive and participatory approaches. Lessons from the TRANSCEND project and the Austrian Red Cross, particularly *Team Österreich*, demonstrate the

value of fostering cooperation and shared responsibility among authorities, civil society, and citizens. Building trust, enhancing household preparedness, and promoting cross-sector collaboration are essential to achieving societal resilience. These recommendations offer a clear path for creating a robust and engaged society, aligned with European Disaster Resilience Goals, ready to face future challenges.

The Austrian Red Cross suggests the following for long-term impact:

- **Create a team spirit for disaster risk reduction and disaster response in Austria:** Promote a narrative of cooperation that emphasises the importance of collective efforts to overcome crises. Highlight the shared responsibility of public authorities, civil society, and citizens to create resilient communities.
- **Clarify roles and responsibilities in disaster management:** Clearly define and communicate the limits of public systems and provide practical advice to citizens on how they can effectively contribute to disaster preparedness and response efforts.
- **Simplify language and create relatable narratives:** Move away from technocratic terms and use positive messaging to inspire action. For example, focus on the benefits of preparedness and collaboration rather than emphasising risks, using accessible and motivational communication strategies.
- **Support civil society engagement and volunteering:** Encourage volunteering and civic participation by providing supportive structures such as insurance coverage, public recognition, and incentives. Maintain these efforts within the domain of civil society organisations, leveraging their expertise and reach.
- **Encourage cross-sector synergies in citizen engagement:** Promote initiatives such as citizen science projects, volunteering programmes, and first aid training to ensure sustained engagement in disaster preparedness and response across different sectors of society.
- **Invest in platforms that foster civil society cooperation:** Allocate resources to strengthen platforms like “Team Österreich,” which enhance collaboration and preparedness within civil society, ensuring a high return on investment for collective resilience efforts.
- **Collaborate with critical infrastructure providers:** Work with providers of essential services to ensure their workforce is prepared for crises. Encourage initiatives that support household preparedness for employees, ensuring service continuity and strengthening community resilience.

In conclusion, the DRS Pilot conducted by the Austrian Red Cross highlights the importance of engaging citizens in disaster resilience through inclusive and participatory approaches. Lessons from the TRANSCEND project and the Austrian Red Cross, particularly *Team Österreich*, demonstrate the value of fostering cooperation and shared responsibility among authorities,

civil society, and citizens. Building trust, enhancing household preparedness, and promoting cross-sector collaboration are essential to achieving societal resilience. These recommendations offer a clear path for creating a robust and engaged society, aligned with European Disaster Resilience Goals, ready to face future challenges.

5 Pilot on Fighting Crime and Terrorism (FCT)

5.1 Organisation of the pilot activities

The Fighting Crime and Terrorism (FCT) pilot was organised by the European Forum for Urban Security (Efus) in partnership with the City of Mechelen in Belgium, the Dutch Institute for Safe and Secure Spaces (DISSS), and a network of youth workers operating in Mechelen, Belgium. The objective of this pilot was to develop and implement participatory strategies for urban security that engage young people in identifying, discussing, and shaping policy responses to the security challenges affecting their daily lives.

The pilot unfolded through a series of three workshops conducted in 2024. Each session was purposefully structured to build upon the outcomes of the previous meeting, creating a cumulative learning experience. These workshops were more than one-off discussions; they were part of a carefully curated journey towards empowering young people to contribute meaningfully to urban safety debates. From the outset, Efus assumed the strategic and operational leadership of the pilot, ensuring that all activities aligned with TRANSCEND's broader mission to enhance citizen participation in urban security governance. DISSS offered its expertise in participatory methodology, with particular attention to creating environments conducive to inclusive and psychologically safe dialogue. The City of Mechelen played a dual role: both as the host municipality and as an engaged partner responsible for mobilising local stakeholders.

Integral to the process were youth workers from organisations such as ROJM (*Regionaal Open Jeugdcentrum Mechelen*), whose role was pivotal. They provided invaluable support by mobilising participants, guiding discussions during the workshops, and facilitating the integration of pilot outcomes into ongoing youth engagement initiatives within the city. Their insider knowledge of local youth dynamics and their trust-based relationships with participants ensured that discussions were grounded, authentic, and relevant.

The methodology adopted across the pilot was firmly rooted in co-creation principles. It was conceived not only to collect opinions but to empower participants to shape the agenda. These co-creation sessions, shaped through the participatory Toolbox developed within TRANSCEND, sought to give voice to those who are often unheard in traditional policy-making spaces. In doing so, the pilot created inclusive platforms where young people, especially those from marginalised backgrounds, could express their concerns and aspirations regarding urban safety.

Like in most security domains, the development of technologies and strategies for the prevention of crime and terrorism often suffers from a lack of citizen participation. The Mechelen pilot focused on the latter. Strategies

are frequently designed through top-down processes that prioritise institutional needs over community experiences. One of the main characteristics of the field is its complexity: urban safety involves a range of actors including law enforcement agencies, municipal authorities, educational institutions, social workers, and, crucially, the residents themselves.

The Mechelen pilot highlighted several recurring **challenges** in this domain. Among these was the persistent stigmatisation of youth, particularly those from ethnically diverse or socio-economically disadvantaged backgrounds. This stigmatisation often results in policies that alienate rather than engage young people. Another significant concern was the growing influence of online spaces on youth behaviour. Participants discussed how social media platforms often act as echo chambers, amplifying harmful narratives and sometimes serving as entry points for radicalisation.

Moreover, the pilot underscored the difficulty of reaching young individuals who have already disengaged from civic life. These youth are often suspicious of institutional initiatives, perceiving them as disconnected from their lived experiences. Institutions, on the other hand, are frequently limited in their ability to maintain sustained engagement formats due to funding, staffing, and strategic constraints.

Despite these obstacles, the pilot also revealed promising **opportunities**. The local government's openness to adopting co-creative strategies, combined with DISSS's experience in designing safe participatory processes, created fertile ground for innovation. Youth workers, operating at the intersection of policy and daily life, demonstrated that they can serve as powerful facilitators of change. Their role in translating institutional goals into relatable actions was one of the most valuable assets of the pilot.

The selection of Mechelen as the pilot location was strategic and deliberate. The city had already demonstrated a strong commitment to holistic and inclusive urban security through previous collaborations with Efus. Its reputation as a progressive municipality, coupled with an established ecosystem of youth engagement, made it an ideal setting for this experimental approach.

Partner selection was equally purposeful. DISSS brought a deep understanding of how to design participatory spaces that are not only inclusive but also emotionally and intellectually safe. Their expertise in methods such as the World Café ensured that workshop sessions would avoid the pitfalls of tokenistic engagement. ROJM and other local youth organisations contributed their extensive networks and operational knowledge of the local context. This multi-actor configuration allowed for a comprehensive and locally grounded implementation of the pilot.

The themes addressed during the pilot were identified through a collaborative process involving local consultations, prior research conducted by TRANSCEND (notably D3.1), and ongoing dialogue with stakeholders.

Three main topics emerged as both urgent and resonant with the target audience:

The first of these focused on the **role of social media in youth security**. Participants explored how platforms like Instagram, TikTok, and YouTube influence perceptions of violence, identity, and risk. This dialogue covered both the dangers and the potential of digital spaces, with many participants expressing a desire for media literacy education and safe online communities.

The second topic centred around **drug trafficking and the criminalisation of youth**. Young people discussed the impact of surveillance, punitive policies, and stereotypes in shaping how their communities are policed. Many argued that the institutional response often fails to account for the socio-economic roots of drug-related activity. Participants called for more support-oriented interventions, such as education, prevention, and access to services, rather than criminalisation.

The third major theme was the question of **institutional trust and legitimacy**. Throughout the workshops, conversations repeatedly returned to the strained relationships between young people and public institutions, particularly the police. A recurrent message was the desire for regular, transparent, and meaningful interaction between institutions and youth. Trust, they emphasised, cannot be demanded; it must be built through consistency and mutual respect.

These themes were unpacked through participatory methods that encouraged reflection, storytelling, and collective problem-solving. The approach helped frame these complex issues in a way that was both emotionally resonant and action-oriented.

5.2 Method selection and Implementation

Efus adopted a participatory design combining focus groups, the World Café method, and deliberative dialogues. This approach reflected the need to foster open, safe environments for youth expression while maintaining a structured flow of dialogue and evaluation. The World Café allowed for informal exchanges on complex themes like surveillance and digital safety, while the stakeholder roundtable in the third workshop ensured cross-sector validation.

These methods were selected based on the TRANSCEND Toolbox's recommendations for sensitive and multi-stakeholder environments and were adapted to youth-specific settings in collaboration with local practitioners. Indeed, youth workers played a central role in recruiting participants, leveraging their networks and relationships with young people in vulnerable neighbourhoods. This was essential to ensure trust and meaningful participation. ROJM and other local organisations helped tailor the invitation process to reflect the linguistic, cultural, and social realities of the young target group.

Despite initial concerns about mobilisation, the workshops attracted engaged participants thanks to careful preparation, co-designed agendas, and the involvement of familiar facilitators.

The pilot in Mechelen was divided into **three workshops**:

- The first workshop was held in familiar, accessible spaces in Mechelen, such as youth centres and community halls. Particular care was taken to create a welcoming environment, with informal seating arrangements, food, and icebreakers to encourage open dialogue. In one session, creative tools such as case-based scenarios (“The Case of Noah”) were used to stimulate reflection and discussion among youth. After discussing the scenarios, the youth were asked to answer three questions using the World Café method. The questions aimed at gathering their needs and points of view on the security issues they may face in public spaces (in the first round, they were asked to identify the key security/safety issues they face in their everyday life; the second round focused on the solutions they might think of; the third round aimed at asking them, “If you had the Mayor in front of you, what would you ask him?”).
- The second workshop was an actual meeting between the youth and the mayor during which they shared the conclusions of their discussions from the first workshop.
- The third workshop was another World Café-designed workshop with some of the project partners, the City of Mechelen, and the youth workers. The aim of this last workshop was to turn the findings of the first workshop with the youth into policy and research recommendations.

The workshops confirmed the effectiveness of small group methods such as the World Café in youth contexts. Combining storytelling, scenario analysis, and structured dialogues helped bridge the gap between young participants' perspectives and institutional decision-making. The second workshop, where youth met with the mayor, proved particularly powerful in demonstrating how participatory approaches can foster legitimacy and build trust in security processes.

5.3 Results of the pilot workshops

The three workshops conducted in Mechelen produced a wealth of qualitative insights that collectively painted a vivid picture of young people's perceptions, frustrations, and aspirations regarding urban security. One of the most immediate outcomes was the emergence of a shared narrative among participants: a call for dignity, recognition, non-discrimination, and agency in shaping the policies that affect their lives.

Participants across all sessions emphasised a strong desire to be heard—not just symbolically, but substantively. They expressed a deep-seated frustration with being perceived as threats or problems to be managed, rather than as partners in co-creating safer communities. This sentiment was particularly pronounced among youth from migrant backgrounds, who

described repeated experiences of racial profiling, over-policing, and systemic neglect. Their testimonies revealed how these patterns have bred alienation and mistrust, further exacerbating the disconnect between institutions and marginalised communities.

Another key finding was the identification of social media as both a battleground and a bridge. While participants acknowledged that digital platforms can be used to spread harmful content or glamorise violence, they also viewed these spaces as essential tools for expression, solidarity, and mobilisation. Many shared that their first encounters with civic engagement or political discourse occurred online. This duality reinforced the importance of digital literacy programmes and youth-led online campaigns that promote positive narratives around identity and community resilience.

The workshops also highlighted a nuanced understanding of the socio-economic underpinnings of crime. Rather than merely condemning illicit activities, participants sought to contextualise them within broader systems of exclusion. For instance, discussions around drug trafficking often touched on poverty, lack of opportunity, and the absence of safe recreational spaces. This analytical depth challenged simplistic “crime prevention” discourses and instead called for holistic approaches that address root causes.

Importantly, the pilot did not only uncover problems—it also surfaced solutions. Young people proposed a wide array of ideas for improving trust and cooperation with local institutions. These included peer mentoring schemes, community dialogues with police officers, participatory budgeting for youth initiatives, and culturally responsive training for public officials. Many of these suggestions were informed by lived experience and carried an implicit demand for sustained investment in youth leadership and creativity.

Moreover, the workshops catalysed new relationships. Several participants reported that the sessions were the first time they had interacted with local authorities or engaged in structured dialogue about safety. For some, this was a transformative moment that shifted their view of what civic engagement could look like. Youth workers also noted a renewed energy among participants, many of whom expressed interest in remaining involved beyond the pilot phase.

Overall, the workshops demonstrated the feasibility and value of co-creation in the context of urban security. They validated the notion that when young people are trusted with responsibility and treated as equals, they can offer critical insight, imaginative ideas, and genuine commitment to the common good.

Participants and facilitators highlighted the value of scenario-based methods and discussion formats proposed in the Toolbox. Youth appreciated interactive formats over lectures, and youth workers valued the flexibility and adaptability of the methods. However, feedback suggested the need for even more visual and digital elements to better engage younger audiences.

These insights fed into the updated version of the TRANSCEND Toolbox and were documented for further guidance on youth engagement in urban security.

The workshops focused on both the digital and social dimensions of radicalisation. Youth highlighted the influence of algorithm-driven social media, lack of trusted mentors, and perceived exclusion from decision-making. Law enforcement representatives discussed early detection systems and community-based intelligence, while practitioners stressed the need for prevention through education and support structures.

5.4 Lessons learnt

The Mechelen pilot served not only as a space for dialogue and experimentation but also as a learning process for all involved—organisers, facilitators, institutions, and participants alike. Several key lessons emerged that will inform future iterations of this methodology, as well as broader strategies for youth participation in urban security.

1. Trust is a prerequisite, not a by-product: One of the clearest insights from the pilot was that trust cannot be expected to emerge spontaneously within a short-term project—it must be built deliberately, patiently, and through repeated gestures of respect and reciprocity. Initial scepticism from participants, especially those with previous negative experiences with authorities, underscored the need for long-term commitment and community presence. The involvement of local youth workers as mediators was essential in this regard, as they served as trusted bridges between young people and institutions.

2. Representation matters, but tokenism is counterproductive: The diversity of the participants—in terms of ethnicity, gender, social background, and personal experience—greatly enriched the discussions. However, several participants raised concerns about being "invited to the table" without real influence on outcomes. This highlighted the importance of setting clear expectations and creating pathways for ongoing engagement. Participation should not end with a single event; rather, it should be embedded in policy-making cycles and accompanied by mechanisms for accountability.

3. Safe spaces require intentional design: The emotional depth and vulnerability expressed during the workshops would not have been possible without careful facilitation and attention to group dynamics. Creating a safe space went beyond physical comfort—it involved establishing norms of respect, ensuring confidentiality, and validating different forms of expression. This lesson is especially relevant for engaging youth who may carry trauma, anger, or mistrust into the room.

4. Co-creation is a skill that must be nurtured: While many young participants brought insightful proposals to the table, the process of structured co-creation—balancing ideals with practical constraints—was new to some.

This revealed a need for preparatory activities, such as training in deliberation, negotiation, and civic literacy. Likewise, institutions must be equipped to listen, adapt, and sometimes relinquish control. Co-creation cannot be reduced to consultation; it demands a cultural shift towards shared ownership.

5. Emotional narratives are powerful levers for change: Stories of personal injustice and resilience resonated strongly during the pilot. These narratives had the power to reframe security concerns not as abstract statistics, but as lived realities. They also prompted moments of reflection among institutional stakeholders, some of whom acknowledged blind spots in their current approaches. Future workshops would benefit from integrating storytelling more deliberately as both a method and an outcome.

6. Flexibility is crucial, especially when working with youth: The process benefited from a flexible methodology that allowed participants to steer the conversation in unexpected but meaningful directions. Rigid agendas would have stifled the organic energy of the group. At the same time, facilitators needed to strike a balance between openness and focus to ensure that discussions translated into concrete insights.

In sum, the pilot confirmed that meaningful youth engagement is neither quick nor easy—but it is indispensable. When thoughtfully designed and sincerely implemented, co-creation processes can transform not only the policies they inform but also the relationships they are built upon.

5.5 Summary and Outlook

The Fighting Crime and Terrorism (FCT) pilot, led by the European Forum for Urban Security (Efus) in partnership with the City of Mechelen and the Dutch Institute for Safe and Secure Spaces (DISSS), was designed to experiment with and refine methods of citizen engagement in the context of urban safety and security. The pilot was a core component of the TRANSCEND project and aimed to address the disconnect between young citizens and institutional stakeholders—particularly in relation to crime prevention, radicalisation, and security technologies.

At the centre of the pilot were three participatory workshops held in Mechelen throughout 2024. Each workshop was conceived as a stepping stone, gradually building a process of mutual trust and constructive dialogue between young people, youth workers, municipal representatives, and law enforcement actors. Participatory methodologies—including the World Café, focus groups, storytelling exercises, and case scenario analysis—were carefully selected from the TRANSCEND Toolbox to match the local context and target audience.

This participatory approach was rooted in co-creation and sought to go beyond traditional consultation. It enabled participants, particularly marginalised youth, to take ownership of the discussions, articulate their concerns, and propose solutions. The active involvement of youth workers and the

deliberate effort to create psychologically safe environments were instrumental to the pilot's success. These elements ensured that participants engaged sincerely and contributed valuable perspectives on issues like online radicalisation, over-policing, and the socio-economic roots of crime.

The pilot was not just about dialogue—it also produced concrete insights and recommendations. These were shared during a capstone web conference held in May 2025, which served both as a dissemination platform and an additional layer of evaluation, involving external stakeholders, researchers, and policymakers. The methodologies tested have proven effective and replicable, with several participants and institutional actors expressing a desire to extend the dialogue beyond the project timeline.

While the FCT pilot yielded significant qualitative results and demonstrated the potential of co-creative methods in the security domain, several **limitations** were encountered:

1. **Temporal Limitations:** The pilot's format, limited to three workshops and one online event, constrained the long-term impact that sustained engagement could have provided. Although the methodology allowed for meaningful insights, the absence of a follow-up phase or continuous engagement structure limited the ability to track long-term changes in attitudes or behaviours.
2. **Scalability Challenges:** The context-specific design of the pilot—built upon pre-existing relationships between the municipality, youth organisations, and Efus—makes replication in other cities challenging without similar conditions. The success of the pilot was largely dependent on the trust that youth workers had already established with participants, a factor not easily replicated in other environments.
3. **Representation:** Although efforts were made to include diverse voices, the number of participants remained relatively small. While the quality of discussion was high, the findings cannot be generalised to all youth populations in Mechelen or beyond. Broader engagement with a more varied demographic would be necessary for comprehensive policy reform.
4. **Integration into Policy:** Despite the enthusiasm of local authorities, there is a lack of formal mechanisms to ensure that insights gathered from the workshops translate into enduring policy change. Without institutionalised channels for youth input, there is a risk that the pilot's outcomes remain anecdotal rather than structural.
5. **Resources and Capacity:** Co-creation processes require significant human and financial resources. Facilitators must be trained, venues secured, and materials adapted for different needs. The intensity of this work raises questions about sustainability, especially when scaling or mainstreaming the approach.

Despite the limitations, the pilot set in motion several **promising developments** that suggest strong potential for long-term impact and replication:

1. **Local Institutional Buy-In:** Perhaps the most significant outcome was the endorsement of participatory methods by the City of Mechelen. The mayor's participation in the second workshop and his subsequent engagement during the web conference signalled a shift toward more inclusive governance. The city has since expressed interest in applying co-creative tools in other areas, such as urban planning, digital inclusion, and youth services.
2. **Strengthening of Local Networks:** The pilot strengthened cooperation between Efus, the City of Mechelen, DISSS, and local youth organisations like ROJM. These actors have committed to maintaining communication beyond the project's formal end. Youth workers who participated in the workshops reported increased interest among young people in continuing civic engagement, with some youth proposing follow-up events and projects.
3. **Web Conference as a Launchpad:** The May 2025 web conference on the FCT pilot acted as both a validation and a dissemination mechanism. It enabled stakeholders from other municipalities and EU institutions to explore the approach, ask questions about the challenges faced, and consider the pilot's transferability. The conference allowed speakers—including municipal representatives, researchers, and youth engagement experts—to reflect on the pilot's relevance to broader European security challenges.
4. **Potential for Policy Uptake:** The recommendations stemming from the pilot have been compiled into a policy brief currently under review by Efus and local partners. This document highlights practical, citizen-informed suggestions for urban safety, such as increasing digital literacy, creating citizen-police dialogue mechanisms, and embedding co-creation into the municipal agenda. If adopted, these could mark a shift in how Mechelen—and potentially other cities—approaches youth participation in security governance.
5. **Replication in Efus Network:** As part of the broader TRANSCEND initiative, Efus is exploring opportunities to replicate the pilot's approach in other cities across its member network. Given that many cities and regions face similar challenges with youth disengagement, trust in policing, and radicalisation risks, the pilot offers a tested methodology that can be adapted to different contexts.
6. **Sustainability through the Toolbox:** Feedback gathered from participants and facilitators has been integrated into the revised version of the TRANSCEND Toolbox. This living document now includes practical tips for engaging youth in complex and sensitive topics, thus supporting future practitioners who wish to implement similar activities.

In conclusion, the Mechelen FCT pilot demonstrated that youth engagement in the security domain is both possible and necessary. When young people are provided with safe spaces, respected as knowledge holders, and invited to co-create solutions, they contribute valuable insights that challenge traditional security narratives. The legacy of the pilot lies not only in the ideas

it generated but in the relationships it built and the methods it tested. With continued commitment, these seeds can grow into lasting change—at the local, national, and European levels.

6 Pilot on Border Management (BM)

6.1 Organisation of the pilot activities

BM technologies form an important dimension of security innovation and require closer attention in the face of contemporary socio-political challenges. Recognising the growing use and potential risks associated with such technologies, the TRANSCEND project selected this area as one to test and discuss its Toolbox for improved citizen participation.

Border management through technological means can be witnessed in multiple sites, from regular border crossing locations (airports, ports, road borders) to locations in third countries where bordering activities take place (for example, through processing of visa applications). In other words, border work does not always happen at a physical border. Often, tech-based measures make border crossing easier for people with the correct passport or visa permits while making it harder for those who do not, including people applying for refugee status, especially if measures are designed or deployed poorly.

In airports, for example, passengers go through various digital checks including passport control and, at times, facial recognition tools. Here, optimisation and efficiency remain important goals for different states to digitalise processes. These endeavours are perceived as crucial to managing the of a growing number of passengers.

Another reason for introducing digitalised tools is to ensure more secure borders. It is believed that technological means could add to the efforts of securing borders against undocumented migration in a more effective manner. Automation, as is the case with many other sectors, is considered key to dealing with challenges faced by current border management procedures. Accordingly, the delegation of important tasks to machines, such as passenger identification, is on the rise.

Security also remains a core goal behind the use of technological means beyond airports. This includes the entry of asylum seekers and refugees around, for instance, coastal areas. Especially in the European Union (EU), one observes an increasing use of technologies for this purpose. This includes drones for border surveillance, 'AI-powered' lie detectors to analyse the truthfulness of the statements made by foreigners, and sensors to spot movements of people (Ahmed and Tondo, 2021).

One must therefore be considerate of the wide array of applications and contexts in which technology is applied in border management. This wide coverage is informed by regional attempts to curb illegal migration as well as the optimisation of lengthy procedures faced by "regular" passengers at airports. Each of the contexts is bound by different challenges.

The use of digital technology to support border management is a tendency that can be observed around the world. Some border sites are particularly advanced in the use of these technologies, such as the US-Mexico border. But the trend is global. For instance, Saudi Arabia recently signed a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with SITA (a leading service provider in air transport technology) for increased digitalisation at its airport. This is being done to facilitate 330 million passengers annually (SITA, 2025).

In this context, there are **two main trends** regarding the use of these technologies at the border. The first is the **use of military-grade technology and assets**, contributing to the militarisation of borders. This includes not only the use of technology that was originally developed for the battlefield (such as drones and AI-powered target acquisition systems) but also the use of military forces and capabilities (such as navy vessels). The second trend is the **growing digitalisation** of the entire process. This is marked not only by the use of digital technologies that automate most stages of the process but also by the reliance on large databases that store data and are becoming increasingly interoperable.

In the case of the EU, the digitalisation of borders is happening in different ways, using various technologies and databases. The most relevant is the Entry/Exit System (expected to be operational late 2025).¹² This system will utilise the Shared Biometric Matching System, which connects various systems, e.g., the Schengen Information System (SIS), Eurodac (containing fingerprints of, e.g., people who seek asylum), and the European Criminal Records Information System–Third Country Nationals (ECRIS-TCN); exchange of criminal records about non-EU citizens and stateless persons across EU member states. All these systems will communicate through dynamics of interoperability.

Interoperability broadly signifies the possibility of making different technological devices work together and communicate. Within the EU's internal security, where it is most prominent, the concept mainly describes a massive data-political project to connect different databases, such as the Schengen or the Visa Information Systems, to 'break the silos'. As explained by Binder et al. (2025), interoperability has been described by the EU's Fundamental Rights Agency, the European Data Protection Officer, and some fundamental rights NGOs as raising several challenges. Having CSOs and citizens excluded from the processes that create interoperability further reinforces these challenges.

Indeed, a key departing assumption of the BM pilot, and in fact the whole TRANSCEND project, is that CSOs and citizens have largely been sidelined in R&D processes that develop security "solutions" in the EU, despite being at the receiving end of the use and deployment of those same technologies. Even though this is problematic across the full spectrum of civil security, it

¹² https://travel-europe.europa.eu/ees_en

is particularly relevant in the field of border management due to its impact on individuals, including many in vulnerable situations.

For this reason, the BM pilot activities were designed to put citizens' perspectives at the centre of our inquiry. During the implementation of the project and also building on previous research projects carried out by the BM pilot team, interactions with CSOs, industry, and security professionals have revealed different motivations and different priorities when dealing with border management. Because CSO perspectives are traditionally less visible, we put them at the centre of our activities.

6.2 Method selection and Implementation

From this perspective, the BM pilot organised three main sets of activities. First, we conducted meetings, interviews, and online consultations with various issue-area experts and CSOs to discuss specific border security technologies and the difficulties faced by CSOs in influencing BM processes. Following up on the lessons learned in the online consultations, two workshops were held in Oslo and Lisbon. It was important to have interactions with CSOs across Europe and to hold the workshops in different locations because the BM reality is fundamentally different across Europe. Keeping this logic in mind generated important insights that would not have been possible if the activities had focused only on one empirical reality.

6.2.1 Online consultations

PRIO organised a series of meetings, interviews, and online consultations with different stakeholders active in the field of border management, from security practitioners to CSOs, to critically discuss specific border security technologies. As mentioned above, collecting CSO perspectives was the main focal point of the pilot. The logic was to first engage directly with CSOs and stakeholders in bilateral meetings and interviews to map the key topics of concern regarding border technologies, so that those findings could guide the design of the two main meetings of the pilot.

The idea was to understand the current state of play when it comes to border management technologies and how civil society can be involved. CSO perspectives were collected from online meetings and exchanges with organisations based across Europe, aiming to get a more detailed and multi-faceted picture of the challenges they face.

The interviews followed a semi-structured format. We had a set of pre-defined questions that we asked, but we left ample room for a conversational dynamic. Creating a welcoming environment enabled the interlocutors to feel they had space to convey their ideas. On some occasions, the interview opened further questions that were then addressed and discussed in online exchanges. Text box 1 provides an example of such post-interview follow-up.

As an organisation working mostly within civic tech, what are the main challenges that you face when wanting to interact with public authorities?

Do you have strategies to engage with citizens and to get their input into your activities or future agenda? If yes, what works better and worse? If not, what could you think to be a way to listen to citizens?

Your organisation grew from a website / blog into a platform that does things in the real world. What were the main steps in building this growth, and what were the main lessons learned from that process?

I know you do not work directly with border management / border security, but from your / DM's experience in the field of civil tech, what would you think would be the main issues to have in mind when designing people-centered systems and technologies?

Text box 6-1: Example of online exchange following up an interview

6.2.2 Oslo workshop – Deliberative workshop

The Oslo workshop, held on the 7th of April 2025, brought together around twenty participants from seven different CSOs and other affiliations. For these activities, we avoided a restrictive definition of CSO, as we also chose to invite members from academic communities such as the University of Oslo and MF, the Norwegian School of Theology, Religion and Society. Most of the participating CSOs were Oslo-based, namely the Norwegian Red Cross, NOAS (Norwegian Organisation for Asylum Seekers), Caritas Norway, *Norges Kristne Råd* (Christian Council of Norway), and Amnesty International Norway. Additionally, we also invited a Greek CSO, the European Public Law Organization (EPLO), which is active in the area of border control in Greece.

The general theme of the workshop was the role of CSOs in security technologies used for border management. It was divided into two parts. In the first part, the participants were divided into four groups, ensuring a diversity of CSOs in each group. The groups were asked to discuss the role that CSOs could play in the use of different technologies for BM. This part of the workshop followed the logic of **focus groups**.

The second part focused on one specific technology: AI-powered facial recognition systems developed for use at airports. Around the world, there is a push to integrate AI tools in border management. A prominent example of an AI tool used for border management in the EU can be found in the European Travel Information and Authorisation System (ETIAS) (Abisola, 2024; Rico and Laukyte, 2024)

A function of this system is to detect identity fraud by analysing machine-readable passports. In other words, AI would help in identifying people who travel using fake passports. Beyond Europe, AI-powered tools are aiding border management efforts. Take, for example, Dubai's Smart Tunnel project. This system—piloted in 2018 for business class passengers—now allows passengers to go through the transit process in an automated manner (VFS Global, 2023). When it comes to the African continent, states like South

Africa, Kenya, and Nigeria are already making use of automated tools for biometric identification. Notably, the African Union Panel on Emerging Technologies (APET) has also been advocating for increased use of smart technologies to protect borders (Bor and Koech, 2023). Similarly, in the United States of America (US), AI facial recognition tools are being used at airports to verify the identity of passengers (DHS n.d.). For border security, fifty-metre-high towers powered by AI can be found in the US. These towers—bearing live surveillance—autonomously decide the areas where cameras should focus upon detecting any anomaly at the border (Molnar, 2024).

Given the prevalence of the use of AI for border management, we decided to specifically focus on it and to invite one representative of a CSO to briefly introduce the topic. The selected CSO was Amnesty International Norway, and the choice was based on the PRIO team's knowledge of their expertise on issues regarding security technologies.

This expert introduction contributed to creating a common ground about the topic in the room, allowing the following exercise to take place. This exercise was a **role play** between a deployer (airport security official) and a developer (a company providing a technology solution). These roles were played by the two workshop organisers, who prepared the exercise beforehand. The remaining workshop participants observed the role play and then developed comments and analysis of what they had just witnessed.

Figure 6-1: Agenda of the Oslo Border Management Workshop

Figure 6-2: Stages of the role play exercise

The role play exercise took place in three stages, corresponding to three important phases of border management R&D and use, namely research and development, procurement, and deployment. For this purpose, we specifically focused on Facial Recognition Technology (FRT) as an example. It was followed by a broader discussion among participants.

6.2.3 Lisbon workshop – Perspective workshop

The Lisbon workshop took place on 14th April 2025. Experts from various CSOs and other organisations based in Lisbon were invited to critically discuss current border management challenges. Participant organisations included *Conselho Português para os Refugiados* (Portuguese Refugee Council), Amnesty International, *Plataforma de Direitos Humanos* (Human Rights Platform), NOVA Asylum Policy Lab, and FiO Legal.

The discussion focused specifically on how recent and upcoming EU legislation, namely the EURODAC regulation and the EU Pact on Migration, will open the door for further collection and use of biometric data. Beyond that, the participants also discussed general challenges they faced in their human rights work in the field of border security and migration.

Figure 6- 3: Common EU System to Manage Migration

6.3 Results of the pilot workshop

The different pilot activities generated important findings regarding both challenges to CSO participation in border management processes and specific challenges brought about by border management technologies. Below are the main findings:

Reputational risk: Working with security technology companies can taint CSOs’ image, leading to reputational risks. While there is a need to improve

the relationship between private companies and CSOs, CSO engagement with both security professionals and the industry can be problematic.

More focus on legal compliance than broader implications: Those involved in the development and procurement of technologies prioritise legal compliance (in a tick-box fashion) more than effectively considering broader technological implications in border management. This presents challenges when systems fail, and developers are shielded by legal compliance.

Limited resources and expertise: While CSOs are willing to be included, they often feel a general lack of necessary resources, particularly due to a lack of funding and capacity in current times. This is made more complex and problematic by the rapid pace of technological innovation. Moreover, as the procurement processes are generally closed, CSOs need more resources to ensure effective intervention.

Heterogeneity of interests: There is a need to understand the contrasting priorities of different parties involved (CSOs, private companies, and authorities). Much could be gained if they collaborated on specific issues. For instance, security companies can develop technology that complies with human rights requirements while authorities could seek important feedback from CSOs. Normalising such coordination could also mitigate the reputational risks for CSOs. The heterogeneity of interests also leads to information asymmetry between the three parties regarding the technology being used for border management. For this purpose, CSOs' intervention is imperative in the initial phases (development and procurement) instead of restricting it to the actual use.

Lack of transparency: Connected to the above is a general lack of transparency that follows border management technologies. The processes of development, procurement, and deployment are often surrounded by secrecy, preventing meaningful action on the part of CSOs.

Varied forms of input were received from the participants of the online interactions and both workshops. More broadly, they focused on the potential role that CSOs could play in the context of border management technologies and the structural issues they face.

The Potential role of CSOs include:

Recourse for aggrieved citizens: Contemporary border management relies on large datasets that gather travellers' personal data. This includes the collection of travellers' biometric data at the airport and other border crossing sites. The treatment of vulnerable groups such as refugees and asylum seekers is also of relevance. In many circumstances, travellers are required to hand over their phones and electronic items to law enforcement authorities without being necessarily informed about how their data are handled. In such cases, aggrieved individuals can approach a CSO for legal assistance. Additionally, CSOs could work on strategic litigation against the procurement or use of border management technology that bears legal risks for citizens.

Human training for meaningful control: With increased automation in security technologies, humans are expected to perform meaningful oversight. This involves consideration of ethical dilemmas facing such individuals and the risk of over- and under-reliance on the automated systems. Taking advantage of their expertise in human rights and ethics, CSOs could contribute to the training of individuals operating border management technologies.

Contextual guidance: Border management covers a wide range of technologies as well as contexts. Border management endeavours for vulnerable groups such as asylum seekers and refugees require a different level of attention compared to border management technologies at airports for regular travellers. In Greece, for instance, borders are heavily militarised due to the influx of a higher number of asylum seekers. Greek CSOs lack access to information about the use—let alone procurement or development—of the technology being used by coast guards. Participants pointed out that there is relatively no space to demand more openness in these processes in states like Greece compared to Norway. By alluding to such contextual needs, CSOs could help inform relevant policymaking.

Formalisation of CSOs' role: Relatedly, formalisation of CSOs' roles is important to ensure that citizens' voices are adequately heard. Currently, CSOs' input is not generally invited in any of the three phases (development, procurement, and deployment) of border management technology, and when it is, it is sometimes through informal channels. CSOs should be included in all three phases. This would also benefit authorities aiming to use any technology, as CSOs could provide critical feedback with special attention to human rights considerations.

Risk assessment: Especially during the development and procurement phases, risk assessment can help avoid legal and ethical risks to individuals. CSOs can assist in performing such an assessment, which can also help achieve 'ethics by design.' Notably, there is also a need to effectively follow the prevalent frameworks. For instance, a framework for Frontex (the European Border and Coast Guard Agency) provides for a consultative forum along with other rules to address human rights concerns during the procurement phase of any technology. It is questionable if those frameworks are adequately followed.

6.4 Summary and Outlook

The BM pilot has shown that citizen participation in border management technological innovation is often confronted with multiple challenges. More needs to be done to ensure enhanced citizen participation. In this regard, CSOs can be of great help, provided that the structural issues are suitably addressed. The activities have also demonstrated the use of new methods for engaging diverse sets of CSOs, which can be followed to gain valuable insights into the challenges and solutions surrounding border management technologies.

In view of the methods used and feedback received, the following recommendations can be made to policymakers interested in increasing citizen participation in border management technologies:

- While legal frameworks struggle to capture technological complexities, parties involved in the development, procurement, and deployment of BM technology should carry out broader ethical impact assessments of a given technology. This should be done in a manner that ensures more accountability and better awareness of the technology.
- Political intervention is needed to formalise the role of CSOs in development, procurement and deployment of BM technologies.
- Involvement of CSOs can ensure greater representation of citizens.
- It is also imperative to focus on development, procurement, and deployment as three different phases demanding separate forms of action to ensure enhanced citizen participation.
- Bringing CSOs together helps not only to point out challenges but they are also well equipped to propose important solutions.

Border management is an area marked by persisting controversies and challenges. It is an area that is prone to politicisation and that directly impacts the travel experience of millions of people on the move, including vulnerable populations. In Europe, these challenges have only grown in recent times, accelerated both by political developments empowering anti-immigration parties and by the growing reliance on technology that is becoming increasingly automated.

At a general level, delegating human tasks to machines might at first seem beneficial, but it also potentially complicates the different roles that humans are still required to play. It is considered an irony of automation (Bainbridge, 1982). Automating border management through machines could also suffer from similar challenges. For instance, the ETIAS is planned to be operated under human oversight. This raises concerns about the effectiveness of human action when identification procedures are automated. Here, the phenomenon of over-reliance on automated decisions, or automation bias, can be problematic.

Regulatory oversight also faces challenges, as many of these tools are applied to meet security ends. For example, we learned in the pilot activities that the data protection authority in Greece lacks the resources to properly investigate the data privacy implications of the tools being used by government authorities (Chelioudakis, 2024). Indeed, privacy and general human rights concerns are repeatedly raised against the use of automated tools for border management. This is especially the case for their use against vulnerable groups such as asylum seekers and refugees. Significant sums of money are being invested by the EU in a variety of technological tools to manage migration, and CSO participation is crucial to widen representativeness and broaden the frameworks for discussion on how to conduct this process in a responsible and legally compliant way.

7 Summary and conclusions

The results of the TRANSCEND pilots in the four application areas in different European cities have shown that the Toolbox “Unlocking Voices. Practical methods to engage citizens in safety and security innovation” can be used in a wide variety of settings to include citizens' perspectives in a wide range of security-related issues and problems. In general, the pilots made clear that there is a need to bridge the gap between the micro level of the individuals who might encounter security or safety-critical situations in their everyday life and the development and regulation of these technologies on a meso and macro level.

The safety and security fields of application were diverse and so were the pilots. This could make a direct comparison challenging. Methods were often combined with each other to fulfil the interest in knowledge and the objectives behind the pilots. The majority of the methods chosen focused on the goal of getting to know people's experiences and ideas and to explore field related aspects in greater depth (Steen, Afghani and Garstka, 2025, Chapter 5).

The methodological reflection on the pilot projects presented in this report makes it clear that a generalisation about the choice of methods according to areas of application would appear to be too simplistic. However, what emerged in the process is that the diversity of application areas is not an obstacle to using the Toolbox and that it can be transferred to different cases or fields. This is both useful and necessary. All pilots underscored the fact that the integration of citizens' perspectives is not a matter of course and was accepted as a rewarding opportunity for unlocking citizens' voices.

The *Cybersecurity pilot* had different objectives for each of the three thematically different workshops. Firstly, it aimed to highlight the importance of adding citizens' perspectives to those of the policymakers and end users from law enforcement agencies. Secondly, it sought to raise awareness of cybercrime among those potentially affected, to discuss possible technical solutions to combat hate speech, and to suggest modifications. Finally, a platform for the secure exchange of health information was discussed in detail with stakeholders and citizens so that the (cybersecurity) technology could be adapted and further developed based on feedback from citizens.

The main objective of the *Fighting Crime and Terrorism pilot* was to develop and implement strategies for urban security by actively engaging with young people in the formulation process. This included identifying the security issues they encounter in their everyday lives and stimulating discussion about the significance of these issues and possible solutions. In addition, participants were given the opportunity to contribute their views and ideas to the design of measures in dialogue with political decision-makers.

The goal of the *Disaster Resilience Societies pilot* was to engage citizens in disaster resilience and relief efforts; to learn and reflect on the role of technology (Mobile App) in disaster resilience; and develop an ever-evolving catalogue and concept of best practices, checklists, and action lists. The aim was not only to raise awareness of disaster risk prevention among various stakeholders but also to discuss with decision-makers how the handling of disasters and extreme events can be organised in cooperation with the population to implement the issue of resilience in a holistic and practical way.

The primary objective of the *Border Management pilot* was to identify the challenges associated with citizen participation in technological innovations addressing security issues at border crossing sites. The otherwise underrepresented perspective of civil society organisations (CSOs) was brought to the foreground. Consequently, specific technological approaches and challenges were discussed, which allowed a joint reflection on how to address these challenges. The pilot project used this approach to shed light on the current state of border management technologies and the associated risks.

7.1 Summary of findings

Overall, we have learned that a sound framework and thorough preparation are necessary for the workshops to be conducted effectively. This includes in particular:

- *A stable cooperation:* between the actors working together to implement citizen engagement (e.g. technology developers, CSOs, policymakers, or scientists).
- *Adequate resources:* Sufficient time, knowledge, and funding must be invested in the planning and implementation of the engagement activities.
- *Good access to the field or group:* It is still not a standard practice to consult citizens in the development of technological systems, even if they are directly affected by them. Recruiting suitable participants is therefore a key issue that should not be underestimated.
- *A common language:* It is important that not only all expectations of the participants are clear, but also that the vocabulary used is unambiguous. All citizens must be able to understand the highly complex field of security research.

The TRANSCEND pilots have also shown that there are various potential difficulties to overcome. First, there is the question of representativeness. There is a significant risk that not all demographic groups are adequately represented, leading to biased perspectives and the potential marginalisation of certain voices. In addition, the complexity of many security-related issues can be a barrier to participation. Issues, especially the exact workings of the technology, can be too complicated for laypeople to fully understand, hindering active participation and informed input from citizens. A

further challenge is that of maintaining the momentum of the workshop and the attention and active engagement of the participating citizens.

To overcome these challenges, it is important to develop well-thought-out strategies and approaches that promote the effective integration of citizens' perspectives. This includes that all citizen engagement activities in the development of security technologies should be guided by four principles:

- *Transparency*: The objectives of the engagement activities, the technologies used, and their potential impact (both positive and negative) must be openly communicated. Sufficient information must be provided to enable understanding of the specific security technologies or applications.
- *Diversity*: To ensure a comprehensive view and assessment, it is important to consider different demographic groups, including minorities and disadvantaged groups. Their inclusion helps to understand problems from a real-life perspective and to consider the resulting needs in research and technology development. This requires measures across all phases of participation (identification of relevant groups and potential advocates, creation of the infrastructural conditions for effective participation, use of suitable methods).
- *Interdisciplinary collaboration*: Technicians, social scientists, civil rights organisations (and others) should collaborate to develop holistic solutions that also address citizens' needs. Involving stakeholders from different sectors of society helps ensure that technical and social aspects are adequately considered.
- *Impact*: The results obtained from citizen engagement must be treated seriously and taken into account wherever possible. This can be achieved by documenting and sharing the results, providing feedback on policy development and the development of technologies. Perceived value added and the meaningfulness of participation are key to encouraging people to engage.

Based on the experiences from all the pilot activities and these principles, we can provide a number of general recommendations on how to incorporate citizens' perspectives into the development of security technologies. These suggestions can serve as guidance for the implementation and evaluation of workshops with citizens (Steen, Afghani and Garstka, 2025, Chapter 7):

Start with a clear purpose and objectives:

- Define a clear and meaningful overall purpose and objectives for the project as a whole—and also for involving citizens in it.
- Align expectations among all stakeholders—citizens, researchers, developers, NGOs.

Collaborate with relevant stakeholders:

- Engage through trusted local partners, e.g., youth workers, NGOs, schools, or community centres.

- Leverage existing networks, e.g., community centres, schools, or hospitals, to find and invite participants.
- Build networks and build trust
- Create multidisciplinary teams, e.g., with tech developers and experts, CSOs and NGOs, policymakers, and ‘ordinary citizens’
- Build long-term partnerships that encourage innovation and embed community insight.

Encourage two-way learning

- Citizens can gain awareness and skills; researchers can gain contextual insights.
- Approach citizens as conversation partners—not just as recipients of information.

Involve citizens (‘users’) in active and creative roles

- Discuss ideas or prototypes with citizens and ask about their perspectives—this can facilitate co-creation and continuous improvement.
- Use citizens’ feedback to improve usability, functionality, and societal alignment of safety and security technologies.
- Proactively include (potentially) underrepresented voices, e.g., young people, migrants, the elderly, or people with disabilities.

Inclusive facilitation

- Choose accessible, familiar venues that help participants feel safe and comfortable.
- Begin with icebreakers or warm-ups to make engagement more comfortable.
- Ground discussions in participants’ everyday experiences—not just technology use.
- Apply participatory methods that encourage expression and reduce barriers, e.g., brain-writing, storytelling, or games.
- Use flexible formats, e.g., parallel workshops, rotating topics, to accommodate diverse perspectives.
- Watch both verbal and non-verbal communication cues, especially around sensitive or controversial topics.
- Integrate practical, tangible examples to explore ethical aspects of technology, e.g., privacy, fairness, transparency, and societal impact, e.g., with regards to surveillance technology or the application of AI.
- Build awareness of issues like discrimination, data value, and informed consent management.

Execute, reflect, evaluate, and improve

- Implement, evaluate, and document—to enable continuous learning and improvements.
- Include structured feedback mechanisms after each meeting, workshop, or session.
- Use evaluation results to further improve, refine, or modify methods.

Shared understanding

It is recommended to first explore which approach will best fit your particular project, and then establish a shared understanding, among the people involved, about which approach to follow. Based on the activities in this section, the following four approaches to involving citizens can be distinguished—which can also be combined:

- Collaborate with citizens **as cocreators**, e.g., invite them to help evaluate and improve a mobile app
- Collaborate with citizens **as research partners**, e.g., invite them to talk about their experiences and needs
- Collaborate with citizens **as conversation partners**, e.g., give them information, and receive feedback from them
- Collaborate with **CSOs and NGOs; they can talk on behalf of citizens**, e.g., about ethical, human rights, and societal aspects

7.2 Conclusion

Online crime, sharing of highly sensitive data, border security and control, safety in urban areas and technologies for resilience against climate disasters: All are aspects of security and their connection to technologies are a significant part of everyday life. Security concerns influence many daily activities, from online interactions to physical safety in public spaces. The social importance of researching the connections between society, politics, technology and the individual at the application level is self-evident.

The involvement of citizens in the development and reflection of security technologies is crucial for several reasons. Firstly, citizens provide valuable insights into their own needs and concerns regarding safety and security, ensuring that technologies are user-centred and effectively address real-world issues. Secondly, engaging citizens fosters trust and transparency, which are essential for the acceptance and legitimacy of security measures (see also Toolbox Section 2).

Our four pilot projects have demonstrated that not only the breadth and width of topics but also the various target groups being addressed make this field highly complex. Different needs, perspectives, and concerns must be taken into account to develop effective and acceptable security technologies or reflect on these to make well-founded recommendations to policy makers.

The diversity of the term “citizens” implies tailored approaches to ensure that all voices of all kinds of citizens are heard and that the technologies function effectively in various contexts. Therefore, it is crucial to consider this complexity factor in the development and implementation of security technologies to achieve a high level of acceptance and effectiveness.

A Toolbox with methods for citizen involvement can significantly enhance this process. Such a Toolbox may include methods like workshops, surveys,

and focus groups, allowing for diverse participation and feedback. By utilising these methods, researchers, developers and policymakers alike can gather a wide range of perspectives, leading to more robust and inclusive security solutions. Ultimately, this collaborative approach not only improves the technologies themselves but also strengthens community ties and promotes a sense of shared responsibility for security.

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